

INCENTIVE
CITIZEN SCIENCE HUBS

D4.1

INCENTIVE Monitoring & Evaluation Framework

Q-PLAN

March 2022

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PROJECT INFORMATION

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Table of Contents

Executive Summary	7
1. Introduction	8
2. Understanding Basic Concepts	9
2.1. Defining Monitoring & Evaluation.....	9
2.2. Existing M&E Frameworks for RRI and CS.....	9
2.3. Outputs, Results, Impacts & Indicators.....	10
2.4. Most Significant Change.....	11
3. Methodology	13
3.1. Overall Approach.....	13
3.2. Co-Creation Exercise.....	14
3.3. Project Objectives.....	15
3.4. Expert Validation Workshop	17
4. Monitoring Framework	20
4.1. Monitoring Methods and Tools.....	20
4.1.1. <i>Method 1: Collection of feedback from CS project participants through CS Project questionnaires</i>	20
4.1.2. <i>Method 2: Collection of data from various CS Hub activities through CS Hub report</i>	21
4.1.3. <i>Method 3: Collection of data regarding institutional changes through RPF0 report</i>	22
4.1.4. <i>Method 4: Collection of data on involved citizens' viewpoints through stakeholder interviews</i>	24
4.1.5. <i>Summary and Timeline</i>	25
4.2. Data Management Provisions.....	27
4.3. Indicators Set	28
4.3.1. <i>01 - Grounding RRI in society</i>	29
4.3.2. <i>02 - Transforming how RPF0s create impact and interact with their surroundings.</i>	36
4.3.3. <i>03 - Advancing sustainable development at local, regional, and global level</i>	41
5. Assessment and Evaluation Framework	45
5.1. Purpose	45
5.2. Assessment & Evaluation Techniques.....	45
5.2.1. <i>Technique 1: Compared with the Targets</i>	45
5.2.2. <i>Technique 2: Compared with the Values of the other RPF0s</i>	46

5.2.3.	<i>Technique 3: Validated by the Public</i>	47
5.2.4.	<i>Technique 4: Compared to Worldwide Trends</i>	48
5.3.	Summary and Timeline.....	49
6.	Concluding Remarks	52
7.	Annexes	53
	Annexe 1 - Co-Creation Exercise Outcomes	53
	Annexe 2 - Expert Validation Workshop Outcomes.....	57
	Annexe 3 - CS Project Questionnaire (Participant)	59
	Annexe 4 - CS Project Questionnaire (Leader).....	63
	Annexe 5 - CS Hub Report	68
	Annexe 6 - Event Questionnaire	71
	Annexe 7 - MSC Interview Template.....	75

List of figures

Figure 1: INCENTIVE M&E Framework Design Approach.....	13
Figure 2: Participant's country of origin (left) and scientific field of expertise (right)	18
Figure 3: Timeline of the INCENTIVE monitoring activities	26
Figure 4: Search interest of the term "Citizen Science" on Google Trends	49
Figure 5: Timeline of the INCENTIVE monitoring activities	51

List of tables

Table 1: Key project objectives	15
Table 2: Overview of the monitoring framework architecture	25
Table 3: Overview of the assessment and evaluation framework architecture	49

List of Abbreviations

AB	Advisory Board
BoD	Board of Directors
CoC	Code of Conduct
CS HUB	CS Hub
CS	Citizen Science
D	Deliverable
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
M&E	Monitoring & Evaluation
MSC	Most Significant Change
O	Objectives
QH	Quadruple Helix
R&I	Research & Innovation
RPFO	Research Performing & Funding Organisation
RRI	Responsible Research & Innovation
SB	Stakeholder Board
SDG	Sustainable Development Goal

Executive Summary

The document at hand is part of the work done under the INCENTIVE project, particularly Task 4.1, “Designing the INCENTIVE monitoring, evaluation and assessment framework”. Overall, the purpose was to co-design and validate the methodology and framework which will be used to closely monitor, evaluate, and assess key project activities’ performance, outcomes, and impacts. A multiple-step approach was followed with significant involvement of external stakeholders, consortium members, partner Research Performing & Funding Organisations (RPFOS) and field experts.

Our work began with a review of key concepts and previous Monitoring and Evaluation (M&E) experience in similar settings. Then, the key pillars of the M&E framework were co-created with the key RPFOS stakeholders in the context of the co-creation workshop of Task2.1. Following that, Q-PLAN, with the support of the consortium partners, engaged in the design of a full fledged M&E framework with evaluation objectives, the methodology to be followed, the indicators to be monitored, the tools (questionnaires) for data collection and the periodicity of data collection. Then, Q-PLAN, with the support of the consortium partners, organised a digital workshop with the participation of 27 M&E experts, in which the framework was presented. The experts’ feedback was valuable for validating our approach and fine-tuning the selected tools and indicators. Finally, the expert-validated and updated framework was discussed with all INCENTIVE partners in a coordination meeting to make any last improvements and ensure that all consortium members are well aware of the notions to be monitored and the type, extent and regularity of data to be collected.

The complete version of the INCENTIVE monitoring, evaluation and assessment framework includes more than 100 indicators to measure progress towards three main objectives: (i) grounding RRI in society; (ii) transforming how RPFOS create impact and interact with their surroundings; and (iii) advancing sustainable development at the local, regional, and global levels. The indicators’ configuration was based on (i) the output of previous Horizon 2020 projects funded by the European Commission, such as MoRRI, SUPER MoRRI, and MICS, (ii) the report from the Expert Group on Policy Indicators for RRI, and (iii) feedback received from INCENTIVE consortium partners and field experts. From this pool of indicators, more than 5 are inspired by the MoRRI project (KPI-10), more than 7 are monitoring relevant SDGs (KPI-11) and more than 40 are aimed at monitoring the institutional changes and events taking place within the RPFOS.

As explained within the current deliverable, the indicators selected will be closely monitored in Task 4.2 through the following key methods: (i) surveying the CS projects’ participants; (ii) surveying the CS Hub activities’ participants; (iii) reporting the institutional changes stimulated within the RPFOS in a dedicated report; and (iv) interviewing key stakeholders using the Most Significant Change approach. Provisions for making data FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) and compliant with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) are foreseen for all methods. In Task 4.3, the collected information and data will be processed for evaluation and assessment purposes. In particular, the values of the indicators will be (i) compared with the targets set; (ii) compared with the respective values of other RPFOS; (iii) presented and validated by stakeholders (through a survey and a few interviews); (iv) and compared to worldwide trends. In doing so, we will identify the strong and weak parts of our approach, understand the specificities of each RPFOS, collect evidence on the societal, scientific, economic and environmental impact of each CS Hub and provide ourselves with a sense of success and areas that could be improved.

1. Introduction

INCENTIVE is a three-year Horizon 2020 “Science with and for Society” project (Grant Agreement (GA) No 101005330) that brings on board four Research Performing and Funding Organisations (RPFOS): the University of Twente, the Autonomous University of Barcelona, the Aristotle University of Thessaloniki and the Vilnius Gediminas Technical University. It supports them to embed Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) related institutional changes in their governance and operating model. The key vehicle to bring about these institutional changes is the co-establishment of their own, organisation-wide Citizen Science Hubs (CS Hubs). The CS Hubs will initiate, support and disseminate Citizen Science (CS) projects with and for their local stakeholder community.

The document at hand is the deliverable (D) 4.1 “INCENTIVE Monitoring and Evaluation Framework”, elaborated in the context of Task 4.1 “Designing the INCENTIVE monitoring, evaluation and assessment framework”. The main purpose is to design and present the framework that will be used to monitor, evaluate and assess the performance, outcomes and impacts of key INCENTIVE activities.

The remaining document consists of the following sections:

- **Section 2** is the outcome of the literature review on previous monitoring and evaluation (M&E) frameworks. It provides the reader with background information and explains the key concepts of monitoring social impacts.
- **Section 3** articulates the overall approach followed to design and fine-tune the INCENTIVE M&E framework, including co-creation with stakeholders and the expert validation workshop.
- **Section 4** elaborates on the selected monitoring methodology, including data collection methods, tools, indicators, responsibilities, data management provisions and timeline.
- **Section 5** elaborates on the selected evaluation and assessment methodology, including assessment techniques, responsibilities, purposes and timeline.
- **Section 6** provides some concluding remarks and guides the project’s next steps.

The **Annexes** include notes kept during co-creation with stakeholders and the expert validation workshop, as well as the questionnaires and forms employed to collect the necessary data.

2. Understanding Basic Concepts

2.1. Defining Monitoring & Evaluation

As a starting point, any M&E framework must be aligned with the project's 'intervention logic', considering the project's objectives, inputs, activities, and output.¹ Appropriate M&E processes can add great value to a project. This realisation has led to a gradual evolution from being perceived as an externally imposed obligation to being perceived as an integral part of the project cycle driven by internal stakeholders².

A proper M&E framework can contribute to efficient project management and appropriate effects assessment.³ To this end, the framework must not simply be a backwards-looking evaluation tool, but a living part of the project that assists a workflow focused on project objectives. Crucially, evaluation is only justifiable if it positively affects a project's beneficiaries and serves a broader purpose, such as improving planning and efficiency or knowledge production⁴.

Especially in the context of RRI, M&E has some specificities. The first is that the European RRI landscape contains great diversity between countries. As this diversity may be rooted in a country's society-science relationships, R&I policy landscape and general civic and political culture, an M&E approach needs to be able to account for these contextual elements⁵. Moreover, the benefits of RRI do not linearly follow an input-to-impact intervention logic but rather process transformations that are embedded within the project activities⁶.

Moreover, due to RRI's inherently normative nature, its evaluation is not just about production and assessment of indicators with the goal of revealing an underlying reality. Rather, it is an opportunity to articulate what is valued within the evaluated and why⁷, and more specifically determining the value of each CS project outcome and process⁸. Considering the normative weight of an RRI implementation, the M&E for such a project arguably represents an opportunity to signify what the future of RRI in European science looks like⁹. Furthermore, monitoring and evaluating RRI through only a quantitative lens can feed an overly narrow conception of its effects and benefits¹⁰.

Monitoring and evaluating CS interventions follow much the same logic, focusing on the 10 principles of CS and their impacts in relation to broader 'domains' such as societal, democratic, scientific and economic. Readers should not consider these domains as separate from one another, rather trying to discern the linkages and interplays between them, so that they capture the depth and complexity of CS impacts. Similarly, to RRI, it is important that impact evaluation of CS initiatives is done relative to context rather than absolute values, again due to the extremely diverse national and regional setting within which these initiatives take place¹¹.

2.2. Existing M&E Frameworks for RRI and CS

Building on the theoretical specificities of M&E in RRI and CS, it is useful to highlight several frameworks which make a practical attempt to monitor and evaluate these processes in Europe. For instance, MoRRI project is one of the landmark studies aiming to monitor European RRI developments through the establishment of indicators across all RRI dimensions. MoRRI's results confirmed the significant diversity within Europe's RRI landscape therefore affirming the need for a contextualised approach built upon a subtle understanding of each state's society-science relationship¹². Building on the achievements

of the MoRRI project, the SUPER MoRRI project (EC, H2020 GA. 824671) works to secure sustained data collection, curation, further evaluation and clarification of the MoRRI indicators. It also develops a more complete scientific understanding of the complicated and diverse relationships between RRI policies and practices and their societal and economic impact.

A further crucial work in this sphere is the European Commission's expert group on policy indicators report for RRI, which adds value by approaching RRI from the network perspective. As such, the expert group posits the development of RRI agendas within stakeholder networks as the main object of monitoring. Or, in other words, they suggest a focus on governance across all RRI dimensions¹³.

Moving onto CS, the work of the MICS project (EC, H2020 GA. 824711) stands out, as it created and implemented a CS impact assessment framework, specifying society, science, environment, economy, and governance as its 5 domains of interest. A key conclusion stemming from this project is that the impact pathways of CS are typically non-linear and that impact assessment of CS is much more than simply impact reporting since it facilitates crucial learning for the future¹⁴. The work of the DITO (EC, H2020 GA. 709443) consortium builds on the concept that CS M&E goes above and beyond traditional narrow conceptions. By highlighting that evaluation of CS activities should serve to further iterative learning amongst ecosystem partners and guide knowledge sharing at public and policy levels. Various reports from DITO also go further in providing practical insights into how M&E should be conducted regarding CS activities, offering an easy to understand and replicable system¹⁵.

Kieslinger et al. (2018) highlight that evaluation in CS is set apart from traditional science projects due to the importance of the participant dimension, placing it on par with scientific, socio-ecological, and economic impacts¹⁶. This can rightly be perceived as the 'citizen' dimension within CS, accepting that evaluation of CS does not go far enough unless we measure effects on project participants themselves and wider society¹⁷. Furthermore, generally, the literature points to a difficulty in evaluating the phenomena, especially in attempting to establish stable frameworks for a still emergent and particularly diverse matter¹⁸. For example, CS evaluation frameworks may have to stray from narrowly measuring official academic outputs, such as journal papers, but look at other societal publications such as newspapers and social media¹⁹¹⁷.

Lastly, the SciShops' (EC, H2020 GA. 709443) materials represent another practically rich addition to CS M&E frameworks, and more importantly, they were created to monitor activities very close to those of INCENTIVE. Namely, SciShops base their approach on gathering data at the micro-level from actual CS project participants, scaling it up to demonstrate that CS can be a valuable source of community-level impacts for RPFOS striving to better fulfil their societal role.

2.3. Outputs, Results, Impacts & Indicators

A typical misunderstanding regarding M&E frameworks is the confusion between outputs, results and impacts. Firstly, **outputs** refer to the direct products of a project²⁰. They are tangible and come about due to specific project activities²¹. The intention is that outputs will contribute to **results**, which refer to a specific dimension of improvement for project beneficiaries, or -in other words- what exactly do we want to change through the project interventions. Finally, **impacts** are the causal link between project outputs and the obtained results. Impacts reflect whether the outputs arising from project activities have caused the intended (or unintended) consequences²².

Indicators can either be concerned with (i) results, in which case they are variables that inform us of specific, measurable features of said results; or (ii) impacts whereby they signal a causal link between activities and observed changes. They both allow us to understand specific issues and facilitate a judgement on how well project objectives have been met. It is useful to set targets for these indicators during M&E framework design and make them measurable by determining their baseline values²³.

When developing indicators for RRI implementations, special care should be taken to align them with RRI practices and goals. Due to the highly contextual nature of RRI in different areas, we must accept that there can't be a standard set of indicators for all²⁴. Because RRI sits between R&I and its surrounding context, an appropriate approach to indicator development can consider them in terms of (i) action (process and outcomes) and (ii) perception of key stakeholders and society. Such an approach can help us understand the interactive character of innovations underlined by complex interplay²⁵. **Process indicators** are used to monitor project implementation accounting for targets, qualities, and activities. **Outcome indicators** facilitate monitoring intervention progress towards set objectives both in the short term (outcome) and long term (impacts)²⁶. At the same time, **perception indicators** monitor how project activities have influenced R&I stakeholder perception.

2.4. Most Significant Change

The 'Most Significant Change' (MSC) approach is a dialogical and story-based evaluation technique that effectively facilitates project improvements because it focuses on changes that stakeholders truly value.²⁷

It entails collecting and interpreting stories about changes in domains that the project intends to create impact. Stories are useful tools to understand project effects because the dialogue is usually focused on concrete outcomes rather than abstract indicators. Furthermore, collecting stories can help all stakeholders better understand a project's achievements, and they also help in delimiting outcomes and signifying different stakeholder values²⁷. Therefore, in many ways, a project such as INCENTIVE, which aims to instigate a variety of impacts along with a complex interplay of different actors and contexts, needs a deeper qualitative method such as MSC to capture some of the subtleties which the quantitative element may miss. Moreover, the MSC approach can reveal which project outcomes hold significance to different stakeholder groups, which fits well with the democratic focus of RRI due to the equal consideration of a wide range of stakeholder perspectives.

According to ITRAC, the seven key steps of any MSC are the following ²⁸:

- 1) **Define domains of change.** The first task in MSC normally introduces the technique to all involved parties, including the staff who will run the process and the stakeholders who will provide their stories. Then the task identifies, with stakeholders, some domains of change, meaning broad areas where change might be expected to occur.
- 2) **Decide how and when to collect stories.** Usually, MSC stories are written down, but other formats such as stories to be recorded as audio or video are possible. Allocation of roles and responsibilities is also a crucial step for a solid operation of the process.
- 3) **Collect significant change stories.** MSC stories are normally collected from those stakeholders most directly involved in a project. They are asked what have been the most significant changes they have experienced or observed within each domain over the past period. The different stories are then written down (or recorded or videoed) – either by the stakeholders themselves

or by other people on their behalf (on an interview-based approach). To this end, a standard template is often used to record the stories and associated information.

- 4) **Select the most significant stories.** People read the stories collected (or listen to the audio or watch the videos) and discuss the value of each story. Then they decide which they consider the most insightful within each domain. The process used to select the stories must be open and transparent, as this is part of what separates MSC from more ad-hoc or subjective methods of identifying stories. The selection criteria and an explanation of the decision should be recorded and fed back to all interested stakeholders.

- 5) **Verify the stories.**

Stories should be checked for accuracy before being used, as otherwise, stories might be selected that are untrue, misleading or open to different interpretations. Verification may involve talking to different stakeholders to find out their views of the change story, or it can be done during the meetings designed to collect and select stories. However, sometimes additional work may need to be done.

3. Methodology

The current section presents the overall approach and the particular steps followed to design and fine-tune the INCENTIVE M&E framework.

3.1. Overall Approach

Experience from previous projects and the GA provisions encouraged a multiple-step approach with significant involvement of external stakeholders, the partner RPFOS and field experts. In particular, designing the INCENTIVE M&E framework was based on the six steps below.

Figure 1: INCENTIVE M&E Framework Design Approach

- **Step 1 – Literature review.** Our work began with a wide literature review to deepen our understanding of monitoring and evaluating societal impacts. We also reviewed previously developed M&E frameworks to gain insights from their design and experience, such as success and prohibiting factors of a solid M&E implementation (see [Section 2](#)).
- **Step 2 - Co-Creation.** In collaboration with Task 2.1 leader (UT), we involved the four RPFOS' stakeholders early in our design process. In particular, they shared with us their perceptions, needs and visions regarding the CS Hub activities that should be monitored and evaluated (see [Section 3.2](#)).
- **Step 3 - Setting the objectives.** After considering relevant GA provisions and the above stakeholder needs and visions, we elaborated on a list with the project objectives that are pertinent for M&E. The INCENTIVE M&E will primarily focus on measuring progress towards those key objectives (see [Section 3.3](#)).
- **Step 4 – First draft of the M&E framework.** The methods to monitor the key project activities and a pool of indicators were defined. The respective tools, including questionnaires, template reports and databases, were also drafted. Finally, the key steps to assess and evaluate the outcomes obtained was proposed.
- **Step 5- Expert validation.** The main pillar of the INCENTIVE M&E framework and an indicative list of indicators were communicated to a group of field experts. Their feedback, collected through a dedicated expert validation workshop organized by Q-PLAN on the 18th of February 2022, was valuable for validating our approach and fine-tuning the selected tools and indicators (see [Section 3.4](#)).
- **Step 6 - Discussion with the RPFOS and other partners involved in activities related to M&E.** The validated framework (methods, indicators, and tools) was presented by Q-PLAN and discussed with all INCENTIVE partners in a dedicated meeting. The aim was to ensure that everyone involved

in implementing the CS Hubs is well aware of the notions to be monitored and the type, extent and regularity of data to be collected, as well as to collect any last inputs/remarks from the partners.

- **Step 7 – Complete version of the M&E framework.** After incorporating comments and feedback from the expert validation workshop and the above coordination meeting, the final version of the INCENTIVE M&E framework was prepared (see [Sections 4](#) and [5](#)). Then it was reviewed by WR and UAB and submitted on time by UT.

3.2. Co-Creation Exercise

Co-creation is defined as the integration of users and stakeholders within the design process and is accompanied by concepts like “co-production”, “public participation”, “collaborative governance”, and “community involvement”²⁹. Its strength as a methodology lies in the capacity to leverage collective creativity in the production of innovative ideas by actively involving multiple stakeholders, each with different backgrounds and views, in the process of designing and jointly creating value³⁰.

Co-creation stands as one of the main normative pillars of the CS Hubs, as they will be spaces where different societal actors gather to co-conduct responsible research and innovation. Therefore, creating elements such as the M&E framework should also mirror this philosophy and thus, be a cooperative exercise. To this end, selected regional R&I stakeholders (e.g., CS experts, researchers, and civil society organisation representatives) were invited to participate in the T2.1 co-creation workshop in September 2021 to co-define key aspects of the CS Hubs, including the objectives of the INCENTIVE M&E framework.

The T2.1 co-creation workshop included four key sessions, and it was co-organised and led by UT. Each RPF0 invited around 2-6 quadruple helix stakeholders, plus a few observers. All participants completed the same exercise; however, they were split into regional groups to gather insights crucial to adapting our outputs to contextual specificities. MURAL boards, which are online visual collaboration platforms*, formed the basis of the exercises. Participants were asked to consider what success looked like in 8 broad impact areas representing INCENTIVE’s desired impacts. These impact areas were chosen to facilitate the effective gathering of stakeholder input, which was later translated into specific project objectives.

After the session, the MURAL boards completed by each RPF0 were aggregated and analysed by Q-PLAN. The outcomes of the co-creation exercise bring out the following important aspects regarding the RPF0s’ goals, which helped us decide which project objectives to monitor:

- The RPF0s and CS Hubs should reach out and inform their local community about CS. Also, they should be open regarding the engagement of citizens and collaborations with groups of stakeholders.
- The CS Hubs should aim to make the knowledge created within them openly available in platforms targeted both to scientists and citizens.
- The CS Hubs should guide the CS project participants regarding the ethical aspects of research and how to follow already existing guidelines and procedures (if available).

* [MURAL is a digital-first visual collaboration platform | MURAL](#)

- The CS Hubs should ensure regional stakeholder engagement in their activities, consult them regarding governance issues, and follow good practices and lessons learned from existing literature and relevant initiatives and organisations.
- The CS Hubs should pay attention to the cooperation and balance between the scientists and the citizens involved in CS projects to evaluate the efficiency of their collaboration.
- Equal gender representation and intersectional inclusion should be ensured in multiple levels, including the CS Hubs’ decision-making, working spaces, CS projects’ research topics, and participants.
- The CS Hubs should aim to educate the local community, researchers, and students about citizen science and RRI by facilitating dedicated training and collaborating with the universities to provide dedicated courses within the Bachelor's and Master's studies.
- The CS Hubs should promote meaningful and innovative research for the local economy and enhance the participating citizens’ hard and soft skills through their engagement with the CS projects.
- The CS Hubs should promote research in environmental and societal welfare that is meaningful to local policy-makers and NGOs and positively impacts the citizens’ everyday lives.

A visual presentation of the results from the expert validation workshop is available in [Annexe 1](#). The insights coming from this analysis, combined with the expected impacts of INCENTIVE (as mentioned in the GA), served as a basis to decide which project objectives to monitor.

3.3. Project Objectives

After considering relevant GA provisions and the above stakeholder needs and visions, we elaborated on a list with specific project objectives (O) that are pertinent for M&E. The INCENTIVE M&E will primarily focus on measuring progress towards those key objectives.

Table 1: Key project objectives

<p>1. O1. Grounding RRI in society O1a. Promoting good practice in CS O1b. Cultivating a more scientifically interested and literate society O1c. Enhancing fruitful stakeholder interactions</p> <p>2. O2. Transforming how RPFOS create impact and interact with their surroundings</p> <p>3. O3. Advancing sustainable development at the local, regional, and global level O3a. Making progress towards the SDGs O3b. Creating societal, economic, democratic and scientific impact</p>

Each objective is divided into parts to monitor specific areas we want to generate results. These sub-objectives are broken down even further into smaller impact domains in some cases. Below you may find a short description of what each objective is referring to:

01. Grounding RRI in society

This objective relates to measuring how the INCENTIVE CS Hubs have contributed to building capacity and engaging all R&I stakeholders in science, especially motivating greater and more substantial participation of citizens and stakeholders in all stages of R&I.

- **01a. Promoting good practice in CS**

This sub-objective will be structured along measuring and evaluating progress towards the ten principles of CS, namely: (1) Active involvement of citizens; (2) Genuine scientific outcome; (3) Researcher-Citizen cooperation; (4) Citizen involvement in multiple stages of the research; (5) Citizen scientists receiving feedback; (6) Robust research methods; (7) Open access to CS project' data; (8) Acknowledgment of citizen contribution; (9) Social value of projects; and (10) Thorough consideration of legal and ethical issues. The analysis will be mainly based on data from the CS projects conducted at the CS Hubs.

- **01b. Cultivating a more scientifically interested and literate society**

This objective is based on how INCENTIVE project activities have affected the proliferation of scientific skills and knowledge amongst citizens, community building between those involved and a general improvement in society's awareness of science. It also evaluates how well we have fared in promoting transdisciplinary approaches and the volume and wealth of knowledge generated by citizens and professional scientists.

- **01c. Enhancing fruitful stakeholder interactions**

Here we are interested in gathering data on the performance of our CS Hubs as sites of inter-stakeholder networking and cooperation in the pursuit of science and addressing pertinent social issues.

02. Transforming how RPFOS create impact and interact with their surroundings

This objective focuses on measuring the support of INCENTIVE activities in stimulating impactful and sustainable institutional changes and the progress towards embedding RRI in each RPFOS. Each RPFOS considers and/or pilots 10 institutional changes, which are products of 96 specific institutional change events. The changes promoted are: (1) Enlargement of R&I activities through CS and citizen's engagement; (2) Adoption of codes of conduct for RRI; (3) Streamlining of engagement with society for R&I decision making; (4) Uptake of R&I standards for socially responsible, inclusive, sustainable R&I processes and products; (5) Adoption of a framework to anticipate the impacts of citizen-science-driven R&I; (6) Adoption of curricula that integrate science and society; (7) Promotion of gender equality in RPFOS; (8) Fostering of open science and open access to scientific results and data; (9) Activation of a mutual learning process across stakeholders of the local ecosystem; (10) New partnerships for RRI across RPFOS. These changes will contribute to integrating the RRI keys of Public Engagement, Gender equality, Open access, Science Education, and Sustainability & Social justice within the R&I processes of each RPFOS.

03. Advancing sustainable development at the local, regional, and global level

This objective focuses on how INCENTIVE has built on creating new pathways for contribution to the SDGs (as defined by the United Nations) and the wider impacts of the institutional changes stimulated by the project.

- **03a. Making progress towards the SDGs**

This sub-objective is concerned with monitoring and evaluating how project activities have contributed to SDG 4 (Quality Education), SDG 5 (Gender Equality), SDG 9 (Industry Innovation

and Infrastructure), SDG 10 (Reduced Inequalities), SDG 11 (Sustainable Cities and Communities), SDG 12 (Responsible Consumption and Production), SDG 16 (Peace, Justice and Strong Institutions) and SDG 17 (Partnership for Goals).

- **O3b. Creating societal, economic, democratic and scientific impact**

Here we will focus on how the institutional changes at each RPF0 have created positive societal, economic, democratic, and scientific impacts in each of their respective regions. For example, co-setting of R&I agendas will stimulate more demand-driven research results, with potentially higher economic impact and may also give more opportunities for participation of businesses in science.

3.4. Expert Validation Workshop

The co-creative aspect did not stop there. The INCENTIVE M&E framework was also expert-validated and calibrated through a dedicated digital workshop with field experts. In particular, the workshop's purpose was to expert validate INCENTIVE's M&E framework by examining its methodology on monitoring, assessment, and evaluation, reflecting on its aspects and providing suggestions. An information document describing the core structure of the M&E framework and the workshop agenda were sent in advance of the workshop to the participants.

The workshop was organised by Q-PLAN. It took place on the 18th of February 2022 digitally on MS Teams and lasted for 1,5 hours. During the workshop, 27 experts were asked to provide their feedback and make suggestions for improving the M&E Framework. The workshop's main approach included the presentation of INCENTIVE's M&E Framework, an open discussion on the M&E framework and a co-validation exercise on improving the framework. During the open discussion, the experts were encouraged to reflect on the information they received and discuss the matters that made an impression on them, ask questions, and share their feedback. During the co-validation exercise, the experts were divided into three digital breakout rooms with dedicated Miro boards and with the guidance of moderators, they reflected on the following questions:

- Which aspects of the project and the CS Hub should be monitored more closely?
- What challenges, bottlenecks, and other prohibiting factors may the CS Hubs face when collecting the required data, and how could they overcome them?

The experts were identified through the author lists of European Commission H2020 public deliverables and publications regarding M&E, RRI and citizen science-related projects. Also, INCENTIVE partners were kindly asked to identify and invite three relevant stakeholders. Finally, twenty-seven experts and three consortium observers attended the Expert validation workshop. Also, 2 Advisory Board members attended the meeting.

Figure 2: Participant's country of origin (left) and scientific field of expertise (right)

A visual presentation of the results from the expert validation workshop is available in [Annexe 2](#). According to the experts' comments, the following elements are the most crucial to improving the M&E framework. More particularly, the M&E framework should:

- offer flexibility and a variety of indicators and methods for monitoring, making it easy to tailor to each of the CS Hubs' needs (governance, funding, cultural, institutional characteristics).
- be considered as an information system and thus, designed as a unity of interdependent factors, which combined can portray evolvement in various sectors.
- aim to associate the impact created by the RPFOS with the quantitative and qualitative characteristics of their CS projects, considering on the one hand measurements such as the number of CS projects, the number of participants and the amount of funding received and on the other hand the scope and the thematics of the CS projects.
- measure the impact that the CS Hubs' operation has on the Quadruple Helix (QH) stakeholders, which includes (i) the way researchers (academics) conduct science, (ii) citizens' empowerment and skill development regarding participation in the commons, (iii) the interest created in the private sector and the local and regional public administration to initiate and/or fund CS projects.
- take into account the resource constraints in data collection and analysis, as well as previous experience (i.e. MoRRI) regarding the difficulties of surveying procedures.
- be concrete about the purpose of evaluation and assessment and thus about the amount and kind of data that are being collected, their value and the parties that can benefit from it.
- select indicators with modesty and critically regarding 'why, how, for whom and what for' this procedure is taking place.
- incorporate narrative-based impact assessment (qualitative) methods to more effectively engage individuals to elaborate on their valuable opinions and include means of offering feedback to the citizens regarding the outcomes of their participation.
- aim to sustain citizens' interest and participation by providing feedback on their participation and by relating to their goals and concerns, including monitoring of (i) the participants' perception regarding their accomplishment and contribution, (ii) their experience with the CS Hubs' and the CS projects' processes in engaging them and in producing knowledge, (iii) their

involvement and eagerness to take initiative within a project and (iv) the continuity of citizen engagement and/or their disengagement.

- monitor the institutional changes within the RPFOS that emerge from and go beyond the CS Hubs, as well as the implicit models and rationales of engagement by the people who fund and set up the Hubs.
- utilise the Eurobarometer as a source of data, in order to integrate monitoring the correlation of the scientific knowledge of citizens and the engagement of citizens in science.
- monitor the training level of the CS Hub researchers and their understanding of the Hub's impact on the citizens involved, on the society, on the RPFOS and on research quality.
- offer adequate options to RPFOS to choose from, regarding the indicators they need to measure, based on the vision of the institutional change they will choose at the beginning of the monitoring process.

After the end of the expert validation workshop, Q-PLAN sent a 'thank you' email along with a document describing the main workshop outcomes to all the participants. In sequence, all experts' comments were considered and incorporated into the final design of the INCENTIVE M&E framework, available in [Sections 4](#) and [5](#).

4. Monitoring Framework

The INCENTIVE M&E framework is divided into two main components. The first component is the Monitoring framework, which collects all the necessary data and information, employing specific methods, procedures, tools, and indicators. The second component is the Assessment and Evaluation framework, which processes the data and information collected to generate useful insights, assess the progress towards the project objectives and evaluate our activities' performance and impact. In the current section, we elaborate on the first component, i.e., the INCENTIVE Monitoring framework.

4.1. Monitoring Methods and Tools

INCENTIVE project, in a nutshell, establishes CS Hubs and creates an enabling environment for CS projects to flourish. It brings together researchers from the RPFOS and stakeholders from the local community in the hope of new and high-quality research results. In parallel, the CS Hubs organise additional activities and events, such as capacity building and mutual learning events, to engage the local community further. Finally, INCENTIVE envisions to spur institutional changes in the RPFOS in order to promote RRI into their R&I activities and governance framework.

In this context, the INCENTIVE Monitoring framework includes several methods to ensure that data and other information are captured at all project levels and from all CS Hub activities. In particular, the key methods employed are (i) collection of feedback from CS project participants (CS Project questionnaires); (ii) collection of data from various CS Hub activities (CS Hub report); (iii) collection of data for the implementation and impacts of the institutional changes (RPFOS report); and (iv) collection of data on involved citizens' viewpoints using the MSC approach (stakeholder interviews).

In other words, the INCENTIVE Monitoring framework adopts a multilayer approach, including both quantitative and qualitative measures and incorporating feedback from various stakeholders (internal and external). The multilayer approach is effective because quantitative study can provide an objective and quantifiable apprehension of the project achievements, while the qualitative method allows us to contextualise and capture the importance of an intervention. This allows us to eventually obtain a holistic view of the performance of the Hubs, the way stakeholders perceive them, and the potential impacts project activities have had. Within the following pages, all selected methods are further described.

4.1.1. *Method 1: Collection of feedback from CS project participants through CS Project questionnaires*

The main activity of a CS Hub is to facilitate the design and implementation of CS projects. Thus, monitoring those projects' performance, outcomes, and impacts is crucial. CS Hubs are encouraged to seek to receive feedback both from the researchers and the citizens participating.

First, each CS project must appoint the role of **CS project leader** to a person, being either a researcher or any other type of stakeholder. Also, each CS Hub must appoint a person employed by the Hub, being responsible for coordinating the data collection (monitoring) activities within the Hub. We suggest that

this role is undertaken by the CS Hub secretariat or any other person with similar responsibilities within the CS Hub.

In [Annexes 3](#) and [4](#), there are two questionnaires aiming to capture feedback from the participants of each CS project (researchers and citizens) and the CS project leader. Both questionnaires should be filled in by the end of the CS project or at M31 (i.e., August 2023) at the latest. In collaboration with the Hub Secretariat, the CS project leader is responsible for collecting answers from both questionnaires. Then, the Hub Secretariat aggregates and anonymises the data and uploads it to a dedicated reporting database (available [here](#)), where only INCENTIVE consortium partners have access.

Method 1 summary	
How is data collected? (Tools)	In Annexes 3 and 4 , there are two questionnaires aiming to capture feedback from the participants of each CS project (researchers and citizens) and the CS project leader.
When is data collected? (Timing)	Both above questionnaires should be filled in by the end of the CS project or at M31 (i.e., August 2023) at the latest.
Who collects data? (Data processor)*	In collaboration with the Hub Secretariat, the CS project leader is responsible for collecting answers from both questionnaires.
Who owns the data? (Data controller)	The respective CS Hub (or the RPF0).
How on-time delivery is ensured? (From design to action)	The partner RPF0 is responsible for mobilising the right people for implementing this method and collecting the required data while adhering to all GDPR provisions. On the other hand, the T4.2 leader (VGTU) is responsible for coordinating the monitoring activities of all Hubs, supporting and sending reminders to the RPF0s, resolving any problems that occur and ensuring the quality of the final results.
How is data used? (Steps forward)	The Hub Secretariat aggregates and anonymises the data and uploads it to a dedicated reporting database. Other partners can use this data for mutual learning purposes. At the same time, Task 4.3 leader (Q-PLAN) can use it for assessment and evaluation purposes.

4.1.2. *Method 2: Collection of data from various CS Hub activities through CS Hub report*

Except for facilitating the CS projects implementation, CS Hubs usually organise various other activities that serve their purposes. For instance, they implement R&I co-creation activities (e.g., R&I agenda setting), capacity building activities (to strengthen science literacy), mutual learning and networking

* The data controller determines the purposes for which and the means by which personal data is processed. So, if your company/organisation decides 'why' and 'how' the personal data should be processed it is the data controller. Employees processing personal data within your organisation do so to fulfil your tasks as data controller. https://ec.europa.eu/info/law/law-topic/data-protection/reform/rules-business-and-organisations/obligations/controller-processor/what-data-controller-or-data-processor_en

events. The Hubs are encouraged to seek feedback from these activities’ participants and aggregate their responses into a CS Hub report.

In [Annexe 5](#), one can find the CS Hub report template. That template is quite generic and includes all the indicators that a CS Hub could potentially monitor. However, the Hub secretariat is welcome to adapt the report to the need and purposes of the specific CS Hub.

The Hub Secretariat must collect the required data, fill in the report and share it with the T4.2 leader (VGTU) in three instances: M23 (Dec 2022), M27 (Apr 2023), and M31 (Aug 2023). The respective data must also be uploaded on the reporting database by the Hub Secretariat to facilitate data utilisation by other partners.

Finally, in [Annexe 6](#), an event questionnaire has been prepared. The CS Hub Secretariat has the option to modify and use that questionnaire to capture the data required. In particular, the questionnaire aims to collect feedback from the participants of all the stakeholder engagement activities organised by the CS Hub.

Method 2 summary	
How is data collected? (Tools)	Data on the CS Hub activities and operation must be imported in a dedicated CS Hub report (available in Annexe 5). A dedicated questionnaire can contribute to collecting data from event participants (Annexe 6).
When is data collected? (Timing)	The report must be shared with the T4.2 leader (VGTU) in three instances: M23 (Dec 2022), M27 (Apr 2023), and M31 (Aug 2023).
Who collects data? (Data processor)	The Hub Secretariat collects the required data and fills in the report.
Who owns the data? (Data controller)	The respective CS Hub (or the RPF0).
How on-time delivery is ensured? (From design to action)	The partner RPF0 is responsible for mobilising the right people for implementing this method and collecting the required data while adhering to all GDPR provisions. On the other hand, the T4.2 leader (VGTU) is responsible for coordinating the monitoring activities of all Hubs, supporting and sending reminders to the RPF0s, resolving any problems that occur and ensuring the quality of the final results.
How is data used? (Steps forward)	The Hub Secretariat aggregates and anonymises the data and uploads it to a dedicated reporting database. Other partners can use this data for mutual learning purposes. At the same time, Task 4.3 leader (Q-PLAN) can use it for assessment and evaluation purposes.

4.1.3. *Method 3: Collection of data regarding institutional changes through RPF0 report*

In our RPF0s, citizen science is used as a lever of change for the broader integration of RRI principles into their activities and operation. Also, the CS Hub can be truly valuable only if properly integrated into the operation of their RPF0. To this end, each RPF0 considers and/or pilots 10 institutional changes through 24 institutional change events. Monitoring the above is crucial to measure and understand the

progress expedited towards the INCENTIVE project objectives. Thus, relevant data must be collected and aggregated within a dedicated RPF0 report.

Later in the project, Q-PLAN will create an RPF0 report template. That template will be quite generic and include all the relevant indicators that a CS Hub could potentially monitor. However, the Hub secretariat is welcome to adapt the report to the need and purposes of the specific CS Hub. For instance, if a Hub focuses mainly on institutional changes promoting gender equality and does not take many actions related to open science, then the Hub secretariat is welcome to exclude (disregard) some of the indicators marked as being related to the later topic. Further instructions for tailoring the RPF0 report will be available within the report template.

The Hub Secretariat must collect the required data, fill in the report and share it with the T4.2 leader (VGTU) in three instances: M15 (Apr 2022), M23 (Dec 2022), and M31 (Aug 2023). The respective data must also be uploaded on the reporting database by the Hub Secretariat to facilitate data utilisation by other partners. The first report (the one collected on M15) will be filled in in the context of T3.1 and not of T4.2. This was agreed between the WP3 leader (UAB) and the WP4 leader (Q-PLAN) as the data collected will be useful also for drafting the Hub operational plans in T3.1 “Citizen Science Hubs’ Pilot Operation Plans”.

Finally, any indicators that the CS Hub did not manage to monitor should be clearly signified, thus providing a view of potentially problematic indicators or issues that are more appropriate for the qualitative method (i.e., Method 4: Stakeholder interviews).

Method 3 summary	
How is data collected? (Tools)	Data on the institutional changes taking place with each RPF0 must be collected and aggregated within a dedicated RPF0 report.
When is data collected? (Timing)	The report must be filled in in three instances: M15 (Apr 2022), M23 (Dec 2022), and M31 (Aug 2023).
Who collects data? (Data processor)	The Hub Secretariat collects the required data and fills in the report.
Who owns the data? (Data controller)	The respective CS Hub (or the RPF0).
How on-time delivery is ensured? (From design to action)	The partner RPF0 is responsible for mobilising the right people for implementing this method and collecting the required data while adhering to all GDPR provisions. On the other hand, the T4.2 leader (VGTU) is responsible for coordinating the monitoring activities of all Hubs, supporting and sending reminders to the RPF0s, resolving any problems that occur and ensuring the quality of the final results.
How is data used? (Steps forward)	The Hub Secretariat aggregates and anonymises the data and uploads it to a dedicated reporting database. Other partners can use this data for mutual learning purposes. At the same time, Task 4.3 leader (Q-PLAN) can use it for assessment and evaluation purposes.

4.1.4. Method 4: Collection of data on involved citizens' viewpoints through stakeholder interviews

Finally, it is of utmost importance for a CS Hub to be in touch with the local community. For instance, it's crucial to know whether stakeholders find good and useful the Hub's activities and if, overall, they appreciate the hub's social, economic, democratic and environmental impact. Thus, the CS Hubs are advised to interview several of their stakeholders. A handy and effective method is the Most Significant Change approach. It is an interview-based approach that asks stakeholders to tell their personal stories of how they experienced the most significant change taking place within the RPFO.

First, each CS Hub must identify at least four internal or external stakeholders who participated in some project activities (e.g., people who participated in any CS projects). Then the Hub Secretariat must contact them and interview them based on the MSC template available in [Annexe 7](#). The template is designed to capture information on all domains of change (aka project objectives), as described in [Section 3.3](#). However, the Hub Secretariat can adapt the questionnaire to the specific stakeholder interviewed. For instance, an academic stakeholder may be best to share stories related to institutional change at the RPFO, while an industry respondent can be asked about the contribution of CS to product development. Also, accounting for time and human resource constraints, if a face-to-face interview is not possible, the questionnaire can be shared with the survey subject via email to be filled in asynchronously. Finally, while the questionnaire template is in English, it is the prerogative of the CS Hub to translate the questionnaires to their native language.

After all stories have been collected, the T4.2 leader (VGTU) must read them and decide which resemble the most significant story within each domain. The selection criteria and an explanation of the decision should be recorded and fed back to all interested stakeholders. The most significant story per domain must be included in D4.2, "Data collection and monitoring of the Citizen Science Hubs", while the remaining stories can be included in the Annexes.

Method 4 summary	
How is data collected? (Tools)	Data is collected through stakeholder interviews. In particular, through a handy and effective method called "Most Significant Change". Each RPFO is expected to interview at least four people from three different stakeholder groups.
When is data collected? (Timing)	The interviews have to be done near the end of the piloting phase in M31 (Aug 2023).
Who collects data? (Data processor)	The Hub secretariat.
Who owns the data? (Data controller)	The respective CS Hub (or the RPFO).
How on-time delivery is ensured? (From design to action)	The partner RPFO is responsible for mobilising the right people for implementing this method and collecting the required data while adhering to all GDPR provisions. On the other hand, the T4.2 leader (VGTU) is responsible for coordinating the monitoring activities of all Hubs, supporting and sending reminders to the RPFOs, resolving any problems that occur and ensuring the quality of the final results.

How is data used? (Steps forward)	The Hub Secretariat aggregates and anonymises the data and uploads it to a dedicated reporting database. Other partners can use this data for mutual learning purposes. At the same time, Task 4.3 leader (Q-PLAN) can use it for assessment and evaluation purposes.
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4.1.5. Summary and Timeline

Table 2: Overview of the monitoring framework architecture

	Monitoring Method	Tool	Timing	Data Processor
1	CS project questionnaires	Two CS project questionnaires, one for the lead researcher and the other for the participants (Annexes 3 & 4)	By the end of the CS project or on M31 (i.e., August 2023), whichever comes first	CS project leader
2	CS Hub report	A CS Hub report template (Annexe 5) and an event questionnaire (Annexe 6)	M23 (Dec 2022), M27 (Apr 2023), and M31 (Aug 2023)	Hub Secretariat
3	RPFO report	An RPFO report template	M15 (Apr 2022), M23 (Dec 2022), and M31 (Aug 2023)	Hub Secretariat
4	Stakeholder interview	A semi-structured interview report based on the MSC approach (Annexe 7)	M31 (Aug 2023)	Hub Secretariat

The above list of monitoring methods and their specifications is the outcome of the close collaboration of Q-PLAN with all INCENTIVE partners. The aim was to find the sweet spot between an M&E framework that is easy to be deployed by the RPFOs, but at the same time complies with all the provisions of the GA, effectively assesses the performance and impacts of INCENTIVE activities, and gathers information that serves as input in other project tasks (T5.1, T5.2 & T5.3). As confirmed during the discussion that took place on the 1st of March 2022 within our consortium, all RPFOs and involved partners are well aware of the notions to be monitored and the type, extent and regularity of data to be collected. However, ad-hoc improvements to the design and content of the M&E framework are possible throughout the project. All partners can propose improvements, while their implementation will be led by T4.2 and T4.3 leaders (VGTU and Q-PLAN, respectively) and will be documented in the respective deliverables (D4.2 and D4.3).

Figure 3: Timeline of the INCENTIVE monitoring activities

4.2. Data Management Provisions

The INCENTIVE consortium handles personal data with due diligence and according to its Data Management Plan guidelines. It respects the provisions set by the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and takes any steps required to make the data collected/generated FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable). In the context of WP4, a few personal details are collected, such as the stakeholder group, gender and job position. Thus, all involved partners must adopt measures to comply with the Art. 5 GDPR principles relating to the processing of personal data.³¹

- **Principle 1: Lawfulness, fairness and transparency principle**

The personal data must be processed lawfully, fairly, and transparently in relation to the data subject. After reading the consent form and privacy policy, all questionnaire respondents must provide their consent to handle their personal data. At the same time, a data subject request form must be provided to them to support any future data requests.

Within the INCENTIVE Data Management Plan, there are Privacy Policy and Data Subject Request Form templates to support this process. In a similar context, a consent form is attached to the questionnaires available in [Annexes 3, 4, and 6](#). However, each CS Hub is responsible for appropriately adjusting and translating the templates to fit their needs and local laws. Also, they are responsible for developing any additional privacy policy that may be needed.

- **Principle 2: Purpose limitation**

The personal data must be collected for specified, explicit and legitimate purposes (i.e., to evaluate the impact of key INCENTIVE activities) and not be further processed in a manner incompatible with those purposes.

- **Principle 3: Data minimisation**

The personal data must be adequate, relevant and limited to what is necessary to the purposes for which they are processed. For example, the responsibility for contacting stakeholders and sharing the questionnaires has been appointed to the partner RPFs. Thus, no personal data such as names and emails must be collected centrally by the task leaders, Q-PLAN and VGTU.

- **Principle 4: Accuracy**

The personal data must be accurate and, where necessary, kept up to date. To this end, checks must be implemented to correct, update, or erase incorrect or incomplete data.

- **Principle 5: Storage limitation**

Personal data must be retained to achieve our research purposes and comply with applicable laws, regulations, and contractual obligations to which the INCENTIVE consortium is subject. For instance, the partners are obliged to retain data concerning projects funded by the Horizon 2020 Framework Programme for Research and Innovation of the European Union for up to five years after the end of the project. After the expiry of the retention period, and unless further legitimate grounds for retention arise, all INCENTIVE partners must dispose of personal data in a secure manner.

- **Principle 6: Integrity and confidentiality**

If applicable, partner RPFs must apply a personal data risk assessment process to identify, analyse, and evaluate the security risks that may threaten personal data. Based on the results of

this risk assessment, they must define and apply a set of both technical and organisational measures to mitigate security risks.

On top of the above, after completing the WP4 activities, any necessary action will be taken to make the data collected/generated FAIR. In particular, no later than 120 days after the publication of D4.3 or any other relevant scientific article prepared by INCENTIVE partners, the data collected/generated will be made freely available to the public. In particular, aggregate and anonymised data will be uploaded to [Zenodo](#), which automatically links to OpenAIRE. Finally, data findability will be fostered thanks to the metadata that will be included.

4.3. Indicators Set

Section 4.3 presents the set of indicators employed to measure the progress toward each of the INCENTIVE objectives. The indicators were configured based on the output of previous Horizon 2020 projects, such as MoRRI, SUPER_MoRRI, MICS and TeRRIFICA, the report from the Expert Group on Policy Indicators for RRI, and the feedback received from field experts and the INCENTIVE consortium partners. Hereunder, they are grouped according to the objective or sub-objective that they are related to.

The reader can find information on the indicator category and the particular indicator identifier on the left side of each table. And on the right side of each table, the reader can find information on the collection tool employed for each indicator. In particular:

- the symbol **M1C** indicates that data is collected using the questionnaire filled in by citizens participating in CS projects (see Method 1 in [Section 4.1.1](#), available in [Annexe 3](#));
- the symbol **M1R** indicates that data is collected using the questionnaire filled in by CS project leaders (see Method 1 in [Section 4.1.1](#), available in [Annexe 4](#));
- the symbol **M2R** that data is collected using the CS Hub report filled in by the CS Hub Secretariat (see Method 2 in [Section 4.1.2](#), available in [Annexe 5](#));
- the symbol **M2Q** indicates that data is collected using the event questionnaire filled in by all activity participants (see Method 2 in [Section 4.1.2](#), available in [Annexe 6](#));
- the symbol **M2QR** indicates that data is collected using the event questionnaire filled in by stakeholders who participated in R&I co-creation events (see Method 2 in [Section 4.1.2](#), available in [Annexe 6](#));
- the symbol **M2QA** indicates that data is collected using the event questionnaire filled in by stakeholders who participated in awareness-raising events (see Method 2 in [Section 4.1.2](#), available in [Annexe 6](#));
- the symbol **M2QM** indicates that data is collected using the event questionnaire filled in by stakeholders who participated in mutual learning and networking events (see Method 2 in [Section 4.1.2](#), available in [Annexe 6](#));
- the symbol **M2QC** indicates that data is collected using the event questionnaire filled in by stakeholders who participated in capacity-building events (see Method 2 in [Section 4.1.2](#), available in [Annexe 6](#));
- the symbol **M3** that data is collected using the RPF0 report filled in by the CS Hub Secretariat (see Method 3 in [Section 4.1.3](#));

- the symbol **T3W** indicates that data is collected using the questionnaire filled in by stakeholders in the frame of Task 5.1 workshop (see Technique 3 in [Section 5.2.3](#));
- the symbol **T3I** indicates that data is collected by interviewing stakeholders (see Technique 3 in [Section 5.2.3](#));

4.3.1. 01 - Grounding RRI in society

01a - Promoting good practice in CS

Category	Identifier	Indicator	Collection
Active involvement of citizens	01A1.1	Number of citizens (i.e., non-professional researchers) that participated in CS projects	M1R
	01A1.2	Number of citizens who dropped out from research before the CS project was completed	M1R
	01A1.3	Number of citizens in CS projects / Number of CS projects implemented	M2R
	01A1.4	Number of CS project participants believing that the involvement and contribution of citizens to the CS project activities has been significant / Total number of CS project participants	M1C
Genuine scientific outcome	01A2.1	Number of CS project leaders who reported "aligning the research question to the priorities of local society" as a key motivation to create the project (e.g., because input from non-experts can provide you with unexpected insights) / Total number of CS projects	M1R
	01A2.2	Number of citizens that reported that their research has the potential to contribute significantly to the particular field of science / Total number of citizens in CS projects surveyed	M1C
	01A2.3	Number research papers that were (or expected to be) written within or after the CS projects / Total number of CS projects	M1R
Researcher-Citizen cooperation	01A3.1	Number of citizens in CS projects / Total number of CS projects participants (including citizens, researchers and the CS project leader)	M1R

	01A3.2	Number of citizens who reported a good collaboration with the researchers in the CS project / Total number of citizens in CS projects surveyed	M1C
	01A3.3	Number of CS project leaders who reported "harnessing the enthusiasm of unpaid experts for science" as a key motivation to create the project / Total number of CS projects	M1R
	01A3.4	Number of CS project leaders who reported "fulfilling career objectives and ambitions and/or gaining recognition" as a key motivation to create the project / Total number of CS projects	M1R
Citizen involvement in multiple stages of the research	01A4.1	Number of CS projects where citizens were involved in "data collection" / Total number of CS projects	M1R
	01A4.2	Number of CS projects where citizens were involved in "co-definition of research questions/theme of study" / Total number of CS projects	M1R
	01A4.3	Number of CS projects where citizens were involved in "data analysis or cleaning" / Total number of CS projects	M1R
	01A4.4	Number of CS projects where citizens were involved into "validation of the output" / Total number of CS projects	M1R
	01A4.5	Number of CS projects where citizens were involved in "extraction of conclusions" / Total number of CS projects	M1R
	01A4.6	Number of citizens who reported that they would like to have been involved in more stages of the research / Total number of citizens in CS projects surveyed	M1C
	01A4.7	Number of citizens reported being motivated by "contributing to scientific research" / Total number of citizens in CS projects surveyed	M1C
Citizen scientists receive feedback	01A5.1	Number of citizens reported the "interest in the theme and topic of the CS project" as a key motivation to participate in the CS project / Total number of citizens in CS projects surveyed	M1C

	01A5.2	Number of citizens interested in receiving information on the outcomes of the CS project that they participated in / Total number of citizens in the CS projects	M1C
	01A5.3	Number of citizens interested in receiving feedback from the CS project leader on their performance after participating in a CS project / Total number of citizens in the CS projects	M1C
	01A5.4	Number of citizens interested in receiving information on the activities and impact of the local CS Hub / Total number of citizens in the CS projects	M1C
Robust research methods	01A6.1	Number of CS project leaders reported that the group of people who participated in the CS project was sufficiently large to allow a robust research / Total number of CS projects	M1R
	01A6.2	Number of CS project leaders reported that they were provided with sufficient resources (e.g., infrastructure, equipment, funding, personnel) to implement their research / Total number of CS projects	M1R
Open access to citizen science project' data	01A7.1	Number of datasets that were (or expected to be) made openly available to the public within or after the CS projects / Total number of CS projects	M1R
	01A7.2	Number of research papers that were (or are expected to be) published in openly accessible repositories / Total number of research papers that were (or expected to be) written within or after the CS projects	M1R
	01A7.3	Number of CS projects doing any of the following: (i) has its own website; (ii) blogs and responds to comments or feedback; (iii) has a YouTube or other video channel / Total number of CS projects	M1R
	01A7.4	Number of CS projects doing any of the following: (i) routinely upload experimental datasets to project websites, with explanatory notes and commentary; (ii) daily laboratory notebooks are written online and publicly accessible in real-time; (iii) regular project dialogue, i.e., a discussion between researchers, partners, and collaborators through a project wiki, is publicly accessible; (iv) employ rich virtual environments for processes of social learning and innovation / Total number of CS projects	M1R

	01A7.5	Number of research papers that have (or will) undergo an open peer review process (i.e., any scholarly review mechanism providing disclosure of author and referee identities to one another at any point during the peer review or publication process) / Total number of research papers that were (or expected to be) written within or after the CS projects	M1R
Acknowledgement of citizen contribution	01A8.1	Number of citizens reported the "rewards (e.g. money, certificates of participation)" as a key motivation to participate in the CS project / Total number of citizens in CS projects surveyed	M1C
	01A8.2	Number of citizens reported "social reasons or recognition" as a key motivation to participate in the CS project / Total number of citizens in CS projects surveyed	M1C
	01A8.3	Number of publications or datasets produced by CS projects citing the names of all involved citizens / Total number of publications or datasets produced by CS projects	M1R
Projects create social value	01A9.1	Number of citizens reported "the project's values or goals" as a key motivation to participate in the CS project / Total number of citizens in CS projects surveyed	M1C
	01A9.2	Number of CS project leaders who reported "making a clear statement that they care about the societal impact of their research and how it works for the public" as a key motivation to create the project / Total number of CS projects	M1R
	01A9.3	Number of CS projects addressing any of the societal challenges that the EU has identified as a priority ((i) Health, demographic change and wellbeing; (ii) Food security, sustainable agriculture and forestry, water research, and bioeconomy; (iii) Secure clean and efficient energy; (iv) Smart, green and integrated transport; (v) Climate action, environment, resource efficiency and raw material; (vi) Europe in a changing world - inclusive, innovative and reflective societies; (vii) Secure societies - protecting freedom and security of Europe and its citizens) / Total number of CS projects	M1R
Thorough consideration of legal and ethical issues	01A10.1	Number of citizens who reported that the activities of the CS project took place in a gender-equal environment / Total number of citizens in CS projects surveyed	M1C
	01A10.2	Number of citizens who reported the absence of gender-inclusive language in the CS project documents or encountered a biased attitude during the project implementation / Total number of citizens in CS projects surveyed	M1C

	01A10.3	Number of citizens who reported that the CS project complied with high research integrity standards (e.g., clarity in the research goals, respect for all participants and transparency in data collection methods) / Total number of citizens in CS projects surveyed	M1C
	01A10.4	Number of CS projects that adopted a methodology for assessing the potential legal and ethical concerns related to their research and identifying how to avoid or minimise them / Total number of CS projects	M1R
	01A10.5	Number of CS projects that aim to research-investigate legal and ethical matters / Total number of CS projects	M1R

01b - Cultivating a more scientifically interested and literate society

Category	Identifier	Indicator	Collection
Impact on participating citizen's scientific skills and knowledge	01B1.1	Number of citizens reported "gaining a deeper and broader understanding of how science operates" as a key motivation to participate in the CS project / Total number of citizens in CS projects surveyed	M1C
	01B1.2	Number of CS project leaders who reported "building pathways by which the utility and impact of Social Sciences and Humanities research can be recognised" as a key motivation to create the project / Total number of CS projects	M1R
	01B1.3	Number of CS project leaders who reported "generating impact for the citizens participating in the CS project (e.g., higher science literacy)" as a key motivation to create the project / Total number of CS projects	M1R
	01B1.4	Number of stakeholders who reported that in the future they would more actively search information about controversial technologies or read related articles and news / Total number of stakeholders surveyed	M2QC
	01B1.5	Number of citizens who reported that in the future they would more actively search information about relevant technologies and scientific outputs or read related articles and news / Total number of citizens in CS projects surveyed	M1C
	01B1.6	Number of citizens reported that they gained a better understanding of how research is performed / Total number of citizens in CS projects surveyed	M1C

Raising awareness of science	01B2.1	Number of citizens reported "gaining a deeper and broader understanding of the topic under investigation" as a key motivation to participate in the CS project / Total number of citizens in CS projects surveyed	M1C
	01B2.2	Number of CS project leaders who reported "making their research more accessible to a wider audience and increasing its reach" as a key motivation to create the project / Total number of CS projects	M1R
	01B2.3	Number of citizens reported that participating in a CS project helped them generate awareness of science-related issues and a positive image of science / Total number of citizens in CS projects surveyed	M1C
	01B2.4	Number of (awareness-raising) events organised by the CS Hub to inform and mobilise stakeholders towards participating in CS (e.g., info days) / Total number of CS Hubs	M2R
	01B2.5	Number of people that participated in the above (awareness-raising) events	M2R
	01B2.6	Number of participants who reported being satisfied by the experience of participating in the awareness-raising event / Total number of participants in the above awareness-raising event	M2QA
	01B2.7	Number of stakeholders who reported that they got involved in the CS Hub activities through a social media post / Total stakeholders surveyed	M2Q
The expansion of citizen science communities	01B3.1	Number of stakeholders believing that public policies must promote co-production of scientific knowledge (e.g., by creating incentives to the research-performing organisations to engage with citizen-science projects) / Total number of stakeholders surveyed	T3W
	01B3.2	Number of stakeholders not previously engaged in a CS project that are now interested in participating in such a project / Total number of stakeholders surveyed	T3W
	01B3.3	Number of citizens reported that they would like to participate again in a CS project / Total number of citizens in CS projects surveyed	M1C
The promotion of the	01B4.1	Number of CS projects where scientists from many different disciplines (i.e., university departments) worked together / Total number of CS projects	M1R

transdisciplinary approach	01B4.2	Number of CS projects that aimed for inclusive research implementing methods to consider the full range of human diversity with respect to ability, language, culture, gender, age and other forms of human difference / Total number of CS projects	M1R
The volume and wealth of knowledge generated by citizen and professional scientists	01B5.1	Number of CS project leaders who reported "resources constraints and/or funding opportunities" as a key motivation to create the project (e.g., setting-up a CS project was a requirement for acquiring a grant) / Total number of CS projects	M1R
	01B5.2	Number of CS project leaders who reported "time and geographic constraints and/or opportunities" as a key motivation to create the project (e.g., they can create large data sets and complete labour-intensive tasks much faster and more efficiently) / Total number of CS projects	M1R
Whether social participation has functioned as a process of learning and knowing	01B6.1	Number of citizens reported that participating in the project has improved their team-working skills / Total number of citizens in CS projects surveyed	M1C
	01B6.2	Number of citizens reported that participating in the project has improved their critical thinking skills / Total number of citizens in CS projects surveyed	M1C

01c - Enhancing fruitful stakeholder interactions

Category	Identifier	Indicator	Collection
Enhancing fruitful stakeholder interactions	01C1.1	Number of citizens reported "fun and enjoyment" as a key motivation to participate in the CS project / Total number of citizens in CS projects surveyed	M1C
	01C1.2	Number of business stakeholders in CS projects / Total number of CS projects participants	M1C
	01C1.3	Number of civil society representatives in CS projects / Total number of CS projects participants	M1C
	01C1.4	Number of policy-makers in CS projects / Total number of CS projects participants	M1C

	01C1.5	Number of citizens believing that the group of people who participated in the CS project was adequately diverse to allow various opinions to be considered in the research design / Total number of citizens in CS projects surveyed	M1C
	01C1.6	Number of stakeholders reporting that the Hub stimulates stakeholder interactions that benefit the entire R&I ecosystem / Total number of stakeholders surveyed	T3I
	01C1.7	Number CS projects participants who reported that they want to continue working with the team formed during the CS project / Total number of CS project participants surveyed	M1C
Networking of citizens involved in citizen science activities	01C2.1	Number of citizens reported "meeting new people and engaging in a community" as a key motivation to participate in the CS project / Total number of citizens in CS projects surveyed	M1C
	01C2.2	Number of citizens reported "potential benefits for my career" as a key motivation to participate in the CS project / Total number of citizens in CS projects surveyed	M1C
	01C2.3	Number of stakeholders who reported that they got involved in the CS Hub activities through a friend or contact that is already partaking in the CS Hub activities / Total number of stakeholders surveyed	M2Q

4.3.2. 02 - Transforming how RPFOS create impact and interact with their surroundings

Category	Identifier	Indicator	Collection
Enlargement of R&I activities that engage citizens	021.1	Number of CS projects conducted in the RPFOS / Total number of CS Hubs	M2R
	021.2	Number of stakeholders believing that engaging citizens in the RPFOS R&I activities must be promoted further / Total number of stakeholders surveyed	T3W
	021.3	Number of stakeholders believing that the RPFOS, given its starting point and the available resources, promoted the engagement of citizens into its R&I activities sufficiently / Total number of stakeholders surveyed	T3W

	021.4	Number of grants received for CS-related research projects / Total number of CS Hubs	M1R
Adoption of codes of conduct for RRI	022.1	Number of elements included in the RPF0 Code of Conduct (According to D2.2, the most common elements to include in a code of conduct are six: ethical principles, values, accountability, standard of conduct, standard of practice, disciplinary actions) / Total number of RPF0s	M3
	022.2	Number of activities to inform the RPF0 staff on the Code of Conduct and help them implement its provisions / Number of RPF0s	M3
	022.3	Number of events or activities conducted to raise awareness about ethics on research and-or relevant good practices / Total number of RPF0s	M3
	022.4	Number of CS project leaders who reported that the CS Hub supported them sufficiently with technical expertise and know-how to comply with RRI principles / Total number of CS projects	M1R
Streamlining engagement with society in R&I decision making	023.1	Number of other R&I activities conducted in the CS Hub with the involvement of citizens (e.g., designing, setting the agenda and/ or managing the RPF0's R&I programmes, co-creation of public policies, evaluation of research proposals applying for funding or other R&I funding decisions) / Total number of CS Hubs	M2R
	023.2	Number of citizens that participated in the above R&I activities conducted in the CS Hub / Total number of RPF0s	M2R
	023.3	Number of participants who reported being satisfied by the experience of participating in the above R&I activities / Total number of participants in the above R&I activities	M2QR
	023.4	Number of stakeholders believing that the RPF0, given its starting point and the available resources, sufficiently promoted the engagement of citizens into decision-making on R&I issues (e.g., RPF0 R&I programmes and evaluation of research proposal applying for funding) / Total number of stakeholders surveyed	T3W
	023.5	Number of CS Hub Stakeholder Boards that include representatives of all quadrable helix stakeholder groups / Total number of CS Hubs	M2R

	023.6	Number of CS Hub Stakeholder Board meetings / Total number of CS Hubs	M2R
	023.7	Number of citizens that undertook any of the following roles within the CS Hub: Secretariat; Facilitator; Community Manager; Trainer / Total number of CS Hubs	M2R
	023.8	Number of stakeholders who reported that in the future they would more actively take part in participatory processes for R&I decision-making / Total number of stakeholders surveyed	M2QR
	023.9	Number of RPFOS with specific action plans and-or established processes for engaging the public into its activities and decision-making / Total number of RPFOS	M3
	023.10	Number of stakeholders believing that the researchers and RPFOS staff are provided with sufficient instructions and-or incentives (e.g., monetary, recognition and promotion) to involve the public into their activities and-or decision-making / Total number of stakeholders surveyed	T3W
Uptake of R&I standards for socially responsible, inclusive, and sustainable R&I processes and products	024.1	Number of stakeholders believing that the RPFOS, given its starting point and the available resources, should have uptaken more standards (protocols, policies, regulations) to promote socially responsible, inclusive, and sustainable research and innovation further / Total number of stakeholders surveyed	T3W
	024.2	Number of RPFOS including public engagement as one of the evaluative criteria for the appraisal of research funding applications / Total number of RPFOS	M3
	024.3	Number of RPFOS including public engagement as one of the evaluative criteria for the appraisal of student theses applications (MSc, PhD, Post-Doc) / Total number of RPFOS	M3
	024.4	Number of RPFOS with formal processes or provisions for sharing information with the public about ongoing or completed research activities / Total number of RPFOS	M3
	024.5	Perceived resistance to change by the RPFOS (i.e., the severity of challenges and barriers to making institutional changes that foster RRI within the RPFOS rated from 1-10, where 10 indicates very hard challenges)	M3
	024.6	Perceived information silos within the RPFOS (i.e., the difficulty of finding information about the current governance framework, regulation, processes, etc. of the RPFOS)	M3

Adoption of a framework to anticipate the impacts of CS-driven R&I	025.1	Number of CS projects employing a methodology or process to anticipate and assess the impact of their research design and potential research outcomes on society, environment, economy, etc / Total number of CS projects	M1R
	025.2	Number of RPFOS requiring and-or supporting CS project leaders to anticipate and assess the impact of their research design and potential research outcomes on society, environment, economy, etc / Total number of RPFOS	M3
Adoption of curricula that integrate science and society	026.1	Number of capacity building activities or events (e.g., science cafés, sprints, seminars, webinars and lectures) organised to improve the capacity of citizens to creatively contribute to R&I / Total number of RPFOS	M2R
	026.2	Number of citizens participated in the above capacity building activities / Total number of RPFOS	M2R
	026.3	Number of citizens who reported gaining sufficient knowledge from the above capacity building activities to be able to participate in CS projects / Total number of citizens surveyed	M2QC
	026.4	Number of activities or events organised to familiarise researchers on designing and/or leading CS projects (e.g., how to engage citizens, how to interact with them, how to utilise their contribution and the principles of CS) / Number of RPFOS	M2R
	026.5	Number of researchers who participated in the above activities or events / Total number of RPFOS	M2R
Promotion of gender equality in RFPOs	027.1	Number of female citizens in CS projects / Total number of citizens in CS projects surveyed	M1C
	027.2	Number of female members in the CS Hub Stakeholder Board / Total number of CS Hub Stakeholder members	M2R
	027.3	Number of stakeholders believing that the RPFOS has established sufficient standards (protocols, policies, regulations) to promote the equal representation of female researchers in the CS Hub activities / Total number of stakeholders surveyed	T3I
	027.4	Number of stakeholders believing that the RPFOS has established sufficient standards (protocols, policies, regulations) to minimise the gender wage gap among researchers / Total number of stakeholders surveyed	T3I

	027.5	Number of stakeholders believing that the RPF0 has established sufficient standards (protocols/policies/regulations) to achieve an equal number of male and female heads within the RPF0 (i.e., minimising the gender gap in promotions) / Total number of stakeholders surveyed	T3I
	027.6	Number of training activities or workshops organised by the RPF0 on gender dimensions in research / Total number of RPF0s	M3
Fostering open science and open access to scientific results and data	028.1	Number of stakeholders believing that the RPF0, given its starting point and the available resources, sufficiently contributed to the adoption of open science practices by its researchers / Total number of stakeholders surveyed	T3W
	028.2	Number of RPF0s that have in place open-access policies or some institutional mechanism (e.g., incentives) for promoting open science / Total number of RPF0s	M3
	028.3	Number of activities (training activities, workshops, videos, document with guidelines) organised by the RPF0 to familiarise researchers with open-science practices / Total number of RPF0s	M3
	028.4	Number of CS projects conducted using open-source software or open data repositories / Total number of CS projects	M1R
	028.5	Number of CS projects that have developed and distributed open-source software (or at least planning to do so) / Total number of CS projects	M1R
Activation of a mutual learning process across stakeholders of the local ecosystem	029.1	Number of mutual learning and networking activities (webinars, digital meetings, etc.) organised by the CS Hub activities to enable stakeholders to connect and exchange knowledge with stakeholders from other similar initiatives / Total number of RPF0s	M2R
	029.2	Number of participants in the above mutual learning and networking activities / Total number of RPF0s	M2R
	029.3	Number of participants who reported being satisfied by the experience of participating in the mutual learning and networking activities / Total number of participants in the above mutual learning and networking activities	M2QM
New partnerships for RRI across RPF0s	0210.1	Number of stakeholders believing that signing a Memorandum of Collaboration between the CS Hubs could significantly contribute to promoting RRI in the RPF0s / Total number of stakeholders surveyed	T3W

	0210.2	Number of policymakers reached during policy outreach activities	M3
	0210.3	Number of stakeholders who reported that participating in the CS Hub activities led or may lead to new partnerships or new networks that promote RRI / Total number of stakeholders surveyed	M2Q

4.3.3. 03 - Advancing sustainable development at local, regional, and global level

03a - Making progress towards the SDGs

We mainly monitor progress towards the following SDGs:

- **SDG 4- Quality Education.** Aims at ensuring inclusive and equitable quality education and promoting lifelong learning opportunities for all.
- **SDG 5- Gender Equality.** Focuses on pursuing the main goal of real and sustained gender equality in all aspects of women's and girls' lives.
- **SDG 9- Industry, Innovation, and Infrastructure.** Aims to build resilient infrastructure, promote sustainable industrialization and foster innovation.
- **SDG 10- Reduced Inequalities.** Includes measures to reduce income inequalities; promote universal social, economic and political inclusion; ensure equal opportunities and end discrimination.
- **SDG 11- Sustainable Cities and Communities.** Include safe and affordable housing, affordable and sustainable transport systems, inclusive and sustainable urbanization.
- **SDG 12- Responsible Consumption and Production.** Aims for good use of resources, improving energy efficiency, green and decent jobs and ensuring a better quality of life for all.
- **SDG 16- Peace, Justice and Strong Institutions.** Promotes the rule of law, transparency, accountability, good governance, and non-discrimination at all levels of government.
- **SDG 17- Partnerships for Goals.** It is a call for countries to align policies, improved and more equitable trade, and coordinated investment initiatives.

Category	Identifier	Indicator	Collection
SDG 4- Quality Education	SDG4.1	Number of citizens above 65 years old that participated in the CS projects and the capacity building activities / Total number of participants in the CS projects and the capacity building activities	M2QC
	SDG4.2	Number of citizens below 26 years old that participated in the CS projects and the capacity building activities / Total number of participants in the CS projects and the capacity building activities	M2QC

	SDG4.3	Number of CS projects with at least one educational resource output / Total number of CS projects	M1R
SDG 5- Gender Equality	SDG5.1	Number of CS projects performing research on gender issues / Total number of CS projects	M1R
	SDG5.2	Number of CS projects led by females / Total number of CS projects	M1R
SDG 9- Industry, Innovation, and Infrastructure	SDG9.1	Number of CS projects whose research outputs can contribute to building resilient infrastructure, promoting sustainable industrialisation and fostering innovation / Total number of CS projects	M1R
SDG 10- Reduced Inequalities	SDG10.1	Number of CS projects whose research outputs can contribute to reducing income inequalities, promoting universal social, economic and political inclusion, ensuring equal opportunities and ending discrimination / Total number of CS projects	M1R
	SDG10.2	Number of CS projects performing research on inequality problems or disadvantaged social groups / Total number of CS projects	M1R
SDG 11- Sustainable Cities and Communities	SDG11.1	Number of CS projects whose research outputs can contribute to safer and affordable housing, affordable and sustainable transport systems, inclusive and sustainable urbanisation, protecting the world's cultural and natural heritage, reducing the adverse effects of natural disasters, reducing the environmental impact of cities, providing access to safe and inclusive green and public spaces, strong national and regional development planning, policies for inclusion, resource efficiency and disaster risk reduction, supporting least developed countries in sustainable and resilient building / Total number of CS projects	M1R
	SDG11.2	Number of CS projects performing research on urban social sustainability issue or urban economic sustainability issues or urban environmental sustainability issues / Total number of CS projects	M1R
SDG 12- Responsible Consumption	SDG12.1	Number of CS projects whose research outputs can contribute to better use of resources, improving energy efficiency, green and decent jobs and ensuring a better quality of life for all / Total number of CS projects	M1R

and Production	SDG12.2	Number of CS projects performing research on the circular economy or renewable energy issues / Total number of CS projects	M1R
SDG 16- Peace, Justice and Strong Institutions	SDG16.1	Number of CS projects whose research outputs can contribute to promoting the rule of law, transparency, accountability, good governance, and non-discrimination at all levels of government / Total number of CS projects	M1R
SDG 17- Partnerships for Goals	SDG17.1	Number of CS projects whose research outputs can contribute to promoting improved and more equitable trade among countries, and coordinated investment initiatives / Total number of CS projects	M1R

O3b - Creating societal, democratic, economic and scientific impact

Category	Identifier	Indicator	Collection
Societal		The societal impact can be inferred by existing indicators, including: 01B6.1, 01B6.2, SDG10.1, SDG10.2	
Democratic	03B2.1	Number of stakeholders who reported that their participation triggered their interest in collaborating with others to solve local or global problems or to participate in relevant discussions-debates / Total number of stakeholders surveyed	M2Q
	03B2.2	Number of stakeholders who reported that their participation led them to increase their interest in R&I decision-making / Total number of stakeholders surveyed	M2QR
	03B2.3	Number of stakeholders who reported that their participation helped them to increase their trust in science and research / Total number of stakeholders surveyed	M2Q
Economic	03B3.1	Number of CS projects conducted through the Hub with a potential to produce a marketable product or service / Total number of CS projects	M1R
	03B3.2	Number of CS projects conducted in a partnership or funded by a private sector actor / Total number of CS projects	M1R
Scientific	03B4.1	Number of stakeholders perceiving CS as a legitimate way of doing research / Total number of stakeholders surveyed (KPI 9)	M2Q

	03B4.2	Number of stakeholders who perceive CS as a way to achieve better research results that can address social demands / Total number of stakeholders surveyed (KPI 8)	M2Q
	03B4.3	Number of stakeholders who perceive CS as a way to produce scientific outputs that are highly relevant to local societies needs / Total number of stakeholders surveyed (KPI 7)	M2Q
	03B4.4	Perceived percentage increase in stakeholders' interest in engaging in science as a result of participating in CS Hub activities (on average) (KPI 4)	M2Q

5. Assessment and Evaluation Framework

The INCENTIVE Assessment and Evaluation framework is set to process the data and information collected by the INCENTIVE Monitoring framework (see [Section 4](#)). It aims to generate valuable insights, assess the progress towards the project objectives and evaluate our activities' performance and impact. In the current section, we elaborate on the design, techniques and tools that will be used in Task 4.3 to perform a thorough assessment and evaluation.

5.1. Purpose

Assessment and evaluation are two words whose meaning is quite close yet different from each other. The meaning of assessment is to review the data about something or someone with the purpose to improve the current performance. The meaning of evaluation is to judge the performance of something or someone by measuring the performance based on existing standards. Assessment is an ongoing process, while evaluation provides closure on the existing process.

In the context of INCENTIVE, we mainly focus on assessing our activities to improve our results. However, we also evaluate the impact of our activities to inform respective policy recommendations and a replication guide. In particular, the purposes of the INCENTIVE Assessment and Evaluation framework are the following:

1. identifying the strong and weak parts of our approach, inferring the success and prohibiting factors and ultimately, improving the INCENTIVE activities;
2. understanding the specificities of each RPF0, its strengths and weaknesses and ultimately, improving each CS Hub's action plan;
3. collecting evidence on the societal, scientific, economic and environmental impact of a CS Hub to trigger interest in Citizen Science and develop relevant policy recommendations;
4. providing ourselves (i.e., all involved organisations and individuals) with a sense of success or failure.

5.2. Assessment & Evaluation Techniques

Four key ways (techniques) have been selected to process the collected data and other information for assessment and evaluation purposes. Each technique sheds light on a different and unique aspect and generates valuable insights. In the beginning, we will compare the values of the monitored indicators with their respective targets. Then, we will compare them with the values of other INCENTIVE RPF0s, and we will expose our key outcomes to public scrutiny. Finally, we will compare a few selected indicators with worldwide trends identified by the literature. The following subsections elaborate on each of these techniques.

5.2.1. *Technique 1: Compared with the Targets*

Target setting is an important tool for clarifying direction and assessing organisational progress. It provides an RPF0 with a long-term vision and short-term motivation. Also, if an RPF0 knows where it wants to go, it will be in a strong position to know whether or not it has arrived at that target.

Setting targets for any organisation is not a trivial process. Thus, Task 4.3 leader (Q-PLAN) will support the four RPFOS in this respect. Initially, Q-PLAN will investigate the baseline situation in each RPFOS considering information from previous deliverables*, the first RPFOS report prepared in M15 (Apr 2022), the country profiles developed under the MoRRI project† and several statistics from the Eurobarometer. This information will serve as a critical input to understand the different starting points of each RPFOS.

Then, Q-PLAN will create a first draft of potential/suggested targets for each RPFOS. Particular attention will be paid to making the target values of all indicators S.M.A.R.T., meaning:

- Specific (i.e., specific about what is to be accomplished),
- Measurable (i.e., to ensure that there are measurement methods available),
- Achievable (concerning the baseline situation identified previously),
- Relevant (i.e., relevant to the direction a CS Hub want to go in), and
- Time-bound (because targets without a timeframe may be forgotten or pushed to the side).³²

Afterwards, the RPFOS will be invited to comment and adjust the target values, considering their realistic circumstances and available resources. The final draft of the targets will be shared with Q-PLAN by M21 (Oct 2022). At the same time, RPFOS must ensure that their staff has a clear idea of what they are working toward and have the tools and resources to achieve the targets set.

Progress towards the selected target values must be assessed periodically. In particular, Q-PLAN will process all the available data (i.e., data uploaded by the RPFOS and VGTU on the reporting database) to compare the values of the monitored indicators to their targets and generate valuable insights. These insights will be presented to and discussed with the four RPFOS in a Data Reflection and Fine-tuning meeting organised in M25 (Feb 2023), M29 (Jun 2023) and M33 (Oct 2023). The purpose is to decide whether the progress expedited is sufficient, whether improvements to our approach are needed, and exchange relevant experiences and ideas.

In parallel, the above meeting will serve as an excellent opportunity to assess the effectiveness of the M&E framework and discuss potential improvements in terms of its objectives, impact areas, indicators, methods of data collection and analysis (e.g., adding new indicators or rephrasing existing indicators).

5.2.2. *Technique 2: Compared with the Values of the other RPFOS*

In addition to the previous technique, inter-RPFOS comparisons can generate valuable insights. Of course, each RPFOS is different from the others in many aspects, including the maturity of citizen science, cultural aspects, and available resources. So, comparing the values of monitored indicators of each RPFOS with the values of other RPFOS can shed more light on these differences. The current technique can

* Including the following: (i) D1.2, “Profiles of the 4 RPFOS: Institutional structure, capacity and needs”; (ii) D1.3, “Quadruple Helix stakeholders’ requirements and motivations”; (iii) D2.1, “INCENTIVE Co-Creation Workshop and its outcomes”; (iv) D2.2, “Citizen Science Hubs governance frameworks and operating models”; (v) D2.4, “Activities of Citizen Science Hubs”; and (vi) D3.1, “Citizen Science Hub Pilot Operation Plan”.

† Deliverable “Monitoring the evolution and benefits of responsible research and innovation in Europe” <https://irihs.ihs.ac.at/id/eprint/4713/1/2018-griessler-wuketich-morri-monitoring-responsible-research-innovation.pdf>

contribute to understanding better the progress expedited towards grounding RRI into each local society and other project objectives. Insights gained from this analysis will be presented to and discussed with the four RPF0s in a Data Reflection and Fine-tuning meeting organised in M25 (Feb 2023), M29 (Jun 2023) and M33 (Oct 2023).

The four RPF0s participating in the INCENTIVE consortium were selected to represent all four country clusters created by the MoRRI project. After analysing the country scores in different RRI dimensions across the 28 EU member states*, the following clusters were configured:

- **Cluster 1:** Countries are characterised by a generally high open-access and ethics performance and a below-average performance across all other dimensions. Greece, where the Aristotle University Thessaloniki (AUTh) is located, belongs to this cluster.
- **Cluster 2:** Countries perform well in gender equality, science education and literacy, and ethics while displaying low performance in governance. Lithuania, where Vilnius Gediminas Technical University (VGTU) is located, belongs to this cluster.
- **Cluster 3:** Countries perform highly in public engagement as an assessment criterion for research proposals, open access and gender equality. However, they display low ethical performance. Spain, where the Autonomous University of Barcelona (UAB) is located, belongs to this cluster.
- **Cluster 4:** Countries generally perform well across all dimensions, apart from gender equality and open access. The Netherlands, where the University of Twente (UT) is located, belongs to this cluster.

The high-scoring dimensions in each cluster will be accounted for when assessing performance. Namely, if an RPF0's country cluster performs well in a certain RRI dimension, higher values should be sought in the indicators from that pilot. At the same time, below-average performance should indicate that those dimensions need to be tracked as improvement areas.

5.2.3. *Technique 3: Validated by the Public*

Technique 3 engages stakeholders in the evaluation process through interviews and a workshop.

1) *Interviews*

In M31 (Aug 2023), when the CS Hub activities are almost completed, the RPF0s will interview four internal or external stakeholders (1 per stakeholder group) based on a semi-structured questionnaire developed by Q-PLAN. The interview shall begin by briefly presenting to the stakeholder the progress expedited towards our project objectives, mentioning specifically the CS projects conducted and the institutional changes implemented within the RPF0. Then, each stakeholder will opine on the impact and significance of those activities, providing their perspective based on their expectations on the project.

Also, the interviews will be valorised to cross-reference the outcomes of the quantitative techniques. In particular, we aim to explore the underlying factors affecting the course of impacts and identify any

* MoRRI was conducted before the exit of the United Kingdom from the EU

“deadweight” or attribution from other projects and initiatives. Overall, to properly calculate social impacts, the following challenges are important and thus, will be taken into consideration through interviews with stakeholders:

- what would have happened anyway (“deadweight”);
- the action of others (“attribution”);
- how far the outcome of the initial intervention is likely to be reduced over time (“drop off”);
- if/how much of the outcome displaced other outcomes (“displacement”)*; and
- what could be its unintended consequences (negative or positive).

Task 4.3 leader (Q-PLAN) will draft the questionnaire later in the project based on any gaps or worth-investigating topics identified during the CS Hub operation and monitoring.

2) *Workshop*

In M32 (Sep 2023), when the CS Hub activities are completed, the RPFOS, with the help of the T4.3 leader (Q-PLAN), will draft a short presentation of their results (performance, outcomes and impacts) in .ppt format. The purpose is to illustrate the achieved institutional changes and their substantial societal, democratic, economic and scientific impact. Then, each RPFO will present the ppt to its stakeholders within a workshop organised in Task 5.1 in collaboration with SDA Bocconi. Representatives from the partner RPFO’s main decision-making bodies (university council, rectorate, etc.), CS Hub Stakeholder Board members, and other key stakeholders will be invited. Following the presentation, stakeholders will be asked to provide their feedback on the performance and impact of the INCENTIVE activities through a dedicated questionnaire developed by Q-PLAN in Task 4.3.

5.2.4. *Technique 4: Compared to Worldwide Trends*

Technique 4 aims to investigate whether the results achieved by the four RPFOS during the INCENTIVE project are superior, inferior, or aligned with the results commonly achieved worldwide. In particular, we pick a few indicators, calculate their final values and trends (i.e., the percentage increase from one year to another), and compare these results with relevant worldwide trends. For instance, Q-PLAN will compare the yearly increase in the number of CS projects attained by the INCENTIVE RPFOS to the one achieved globally, as reported by literature (e.g., 10% globally, according to Pocock et al., 2017). Also, Q-PLAN will compare the yearly improvement of citizens’ awareness of CS attained by the INCENTIVE RPFOS compared to the one achieved globally (e.g., 6% globally, according to data retrieved from Google Trends).

* For example: by reducing crime rates in neighbourhood A, crime rates may actually increase in neighbourhood B. In this scenario, we commonly say that crime has been displaced instead of reduced

Figure 4: Search interest of the term “Citizen Science” on Google Trends

5.3. Summary and Timeline

Table 3: Overview of the assessment and evaluation framework architecture

	Method	Key roles, tools & timing
1	Indicator values to be compared with their targets	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Q-PLAN will investigate the baseline situation in M19. Q-PLAN will create a first draft of the targets for each RPFO in M20. RPFOs will comment and adjust the target values in M21. Q-PLAN will process the data and present key insights in a Data Reflection and Fine-tuning meeting organised in M25, M29 and M33.
2	Indicator values to be compared with the values of other RPFOs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Q-PLAN will process the data and present key insights in a Data Reflection and Fine-tuning meeting organised in M25, M29 and M33.
3	Indicator values to be exposed to public scrutiny	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Q-PLAN will develop a semi-structured questionnaire by M30. RPFOs will interview four stakeholders in M31. RPFOs, with the help of Q-PLAN, will draft a short .ppt of their results in M32. Q-PLAN will develop the workshop questionnaire by M32. Q-PLAN, in collaboration with the RPFOs and SDA Bocconi, will receive feedback from the participants of workshops under T5.1 by M33. Q-PLAN will analyse and synthesize the results by M34.
4	Indicator values to be compared to worldwide trends	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Q-PLAN will pick a few indicators and compare the results with relevant worldwide trends by M34.

The above list of assessment and evaluation methods and their specifications is the outcome of the close collaboration of Q-PLAN with all INCENTIVE partners. The aim was to find the sweet spot between an M&E framework that is easy to be deployed by the RPFOs, but at the same time complies with all the provisions of the GA, effectively assess the performance and impacts of INCENTIVE activities, and gathers information that serves as input in other project tasks. As confirmed during the discussion that took place on the 1st of March 2022 within our consortium, all RPFOs and involved partners are well

aware of the notions to be assessed/evaluated and the respective techniques. However, ad-hoc improvements to the design and content of the M&E framework are possible throughout the project. All partners can propose improvements, while their implementation will be led by T4.2 and T4.3 leaders (VGTU and Q-PLAN, respectively) and will be documented in the respective deliverables (D4.2 and D4.3).

Figure 5: Timeline of the INCENTIVE monitoring activities

6. Concluding Remarks

The INCENTIVE M&E framework aims to capture the progress towards (i) grounding RRI within society, (ii) transforming how RPFOS create impact and interact with their surroundings, and (iii) advancing sustainable development at the local, regional, and global levels. It includes more than 100 indicators, with more than 5 inspired by the MoRRI project (**KPI-10**), more than 7 monitoring relevant SDGs (**KPI-11**) and more than 40 aimed at monitoring at least 24 institutional change events per CS Hub.

The implementation of the M&E framework will kick off later in the project, with the compilation of a baseline report by each RPFOS. In particular, in Task 4.2, data will be collected through four key methods, reported in six baseline and periodic reports and ultimately uploaded to a reporting database. RPFOS are encouraged to use the templates available in the Annexes of this deliverable to facilitate monitoring. These templates are generic and include all the indicators that a CS Hub could potentially measure. However, the Hub secretariat is welcome to adapt them to the needs and purposes of the specific CS Hub. Also, each CS Hub is responsible for appropriately adjusting and translating the Privacy Policy and Data Subject Request Form templates available in the INCENTIVE Data Management Plan to fit their needs and local laws. Later in the project, in Task 4.3, data collected will be processed and synthesized to produce valuable insights using four main techniques. Altogether, these tasks will result in a final document (D4.3) presenting the performance, outcomes and impacts of the INCENTIVE project.

7. Annexes

Annexe 1 - Co-Creation Exercise Outcomes

UT M&E Framework Co-Creation Exercise

AUTH M&E Framework Co-Creation Exercise

Co-Creating the Incentive M&E Framework

Co-Creating the Incentive M&E Framework

Public Engagement

- Dissemination of info on how to participate in CS activities (what kind of projects exist)
- Information on how business can support CS hub and different CS project as part of their Corporate Social responsibility programmes
- Increasing the awareness of public on WHAT citizen science is and how it is beneficial for them
- Collaboration with Lithuanian Citizen Science Association (www.pileciumokstas.lt)
- Sharing of the success stories (CS projects that were implemented successfully internationally since we don't have any well-known local projects)
- Exploitation of local media & network of university for dissemination

Open Access

- Developed links and relationships which different Open access data basis
- Development of online repository where all data will be stored and available to be used to more research projects
- Working with Lithuanian CS association on developing materials on why open access is necessary in current academic setting

Ethics

- Establish connections with Ethics Committee in VGTV & present the possible pitfalls of cooperation with citizens
- Prepare best practice case studies highlighting the ethics aspects developed for researchers to analyze
- Establishing connections with Lithuanian Ombudsmen of Academic Ethics

Governance

- Clear decentralized structure: equal distribution and fair participation
- Since most stakeholders and researchers are not aware of CS - build relationships with different scientific associations
- Focus on few stakeholder groups first (e.g. scientists and students) for more focused results. Aiming to reach too many groups would limit the impact given the limited resources
- Include decision-makers at the university level: to introduce them to the concept and activities of CS

Gender Equality

- Equal gender representation in CS hub decision making, working spaces, research topics and representation

Scientific/Science Education

- Introduce training on the principles of CS to Lithuanian scientists (no material is currently available in Lithuanian)
- Include students into the research on CS applicability (e.g. through bachelor or master thesis)
- Prepare and give lectures to students (high-school & university) on CS and open science >> spreading awareness on how they could be involved into science

Economic

- Highlight potential contribution of CS to creation of society welfare > for greater awareness
- Highlight economic benefits of synergies between academia and different stakeholder groups (what they will "get" in return?) > for greater awareness which hopefully will lead to more support (financial resources, human resources)

Sustainability & Societal

- By opening the process of scientific research to general public we aim to Increase the trust in science (huge problem in the current covid-19 context)
- Dissemination of information (methodology, best practice examples) on how other institutions in the region can establish CS hubs

Co-Creating the Incentive M&E Framework

Public Engagement

Open Access

Ethics

Governance

Gender Equality

Scientific/Science Education

Economic

Sustainability & Societal

Annexe 2 – Expert Validation Workshop Outcomes

Annexe 3 - CS Project Questionnaire (Participant)

INFORMED CONSENT FORM

Thank you for starting a research project at our CS Hub! We are sharing with you the following questionnaire in the context of INCENTIVE, a project funded by the European Union under the Horizon 2020 Framework Programme for Research and Innovation. A detailed description of how we handle personal data is presented in the Privacy Policy that can be accessed [here](#).

CS Hub:

CS Hub name:

Address:

Phone: Email:

Responsible persons:

#	Role	Name	E-mail
1			
2			

What do we need from you?

We need you to participate in a short survey. It won't take you more than 10 minutes. Your replies will help us to evaluate the performance and impact of the key project activities. In this context, we need to process some of your personal data:

- Some basic demographics (gender, stakeholder group);
- Your opinions on the subject matter.

What will we do with your data?

The project's deliverables that the survey will derive will not include your personal data or any other information that could identify you. However, we are obliged to grant access to your data to:

- EU officials such as our Project Officer for purposes related to project's evaluation;
- EU agencies and other authorities for project's auditing purposes.

How can you withdraw your consent?

You can withdraw your consent at any time by communicating by email with the responsible persons listed above.

I hereby give my consent to the processing of my personal data needed for:

#	Consent Subject	Tick box
1	My participation in a survey that will be carried out by INCENTIVE to evaluate the performance and impact of key project activities, such as outreach events and educational trainings.	

QUESTIONNAIRE

Which is your key motivation to participate in the Citizen Science (CS) project? *Please select a maximum of 3 answers.*

- contributing to scientific research (O1A4.7)
- gaining a deeper and broader understanding of how science operates (O1B1.1)
- interest in the theme and topic of the CS project (O1A5.1)
- the project's values or goals (O1A9.1)
- gaining a deeper and broader understanding of the topic under investigation (O1B2.1)
- fun and enjoyment (O1C1.1)
- meeting new people and engaging in a community (O1C2.1)
- potential benefits for my career (O1C2.2)
- social reasons or recognition (O1A8.2)
- rewards (e.g. money, certificates of participation) (O1A8.1)

Please reply to the following questions.

#	Identifier	Question	Very much	Some what	Undecided	Not really	Not at all	Don't know
1	O1A10.1	Do you believe that the CS project took place in a gender-equal environment?						
2	O1A10.2	Did you observe any sexist language in the CS project documents, or did you encounter a biased attitude during the project implementation?						
3	O1A10.3	Do you believe that the CS project activities complied with research integrity standards (e.g., clarity in the research goals, respect for all participants and transparency in data collection methods)?						
4	O1C1.5	Do you believe that the group of people who participated in the CS project activities was adequately diverse to allow various opinions to be considered in the research design?						
5	O1A3.2	Did you have a good collaboration with the researchers in the CS project?						

6	01A1.4	Would you assess the contribution of citizens to the CS project activities as “significant”?						
7	01A4.6	Would you like to have been involved in more stages and activities of the research?						

Please reply to the following questions.

#	Identifier	Question	Very much	Some what	Undecided	Not really	Not at all	Don't know
1	01A2.2	Do you think that the current CS project has the potential to contribute significantly to its field of science?						
2	01B1.5	In the future, would you more actively search for information about relevant technologies and scientific outputs or read related articles and news?						
3	01B1.6	Did your participation in the CS project improve your understanding of how research is performed?						
4	01B2.3	Did your participation in the CS project improve your awareness of science-related issues and create a more positive image of science?						
5	01B6.1	Did your participation in the CS project improve your team-working skills?						
6	01B6.2	Did your participation in the CS project improve your critical thinking skills?						

What is your age range?

- <26 (SDG4.2)
- 26-45
- 46-65
- >65 (SDG4.1)

You participated in this survey as a member of:

- academia or research/ education
- governmental body / regional authority (O1C1.4)
- business (O1C1.2)
- civil society organisation (such as NGO representative) (O1C1.3)
- local community
- other (please specify)

Gender: How do you identify? (O27.1)

- Man
- Non-binary
- Woman
- I prefer to self describe, below:

Please reply to the following questions.

#	Identifier	Question	Very much	Some what	Undecided	Not really	Not at all	Don't know
1	O1B3.3	Would you like to participate again in a CS project?						
2	O1C1.7	Would you like to continue working with the particular group of people formed during the CS project?						

What did you like the most about participating in this particular CS project, or which aspect did you consider a weak part?

Please tick if you are interested.

1	O1A5.2	Would you like to receive information on the current CS project's outcomes (scientific outputs, social impacts, etc.)?	
2	O1A5.3	Would you like to receive feedback on your performance from the CS project leader when the CS project is completed?	
3	O1A5.4	Would you like to receive overall information on the CS Hub's activities and social impact?	

Annexe 4 - CS Project Questionnaire (Leader)

INFORMED CONSENT FORM

Thank you for starting a research project at our CS Hub! We are sharing with you the following questionnaire in the context of INCENTIVE, a project funded by the European Union under the Horizon 2020 Framework Programme for Research and Innovation. A detailed description of how we handle personal data is presented in the Privacy Policy that can be accessed [here](#).

CS Hub:

CS Hub name:

Address:

Phone: Email:

Responsible persons:

#	Role	Name	E-mail
1			
2			

What do we need from you?

We need you to participate in a short survey. It won't take you more than 10 minutes. Your replies will help us to evaluate the performance and impact of the key project activities. In this context, we need to process some of your personal data:

- Some basic demographics (gender, stakeholder group);
- Your opinions on the subject matter.

What will we do with your data?

The project's deliverables that the survey will derive will not include your personal data or any other information that could identify you. However, we are obliged to grant access to your data to:

- EU officials such as our Project Officer for purposes related to project's evaluation;
- EU agencies and other authorities for project's auditing purposes.

How can you withdraw your consent?

You can withdraw your consent at any time by communicating by email with the responsible persons listed above.

I hereby give my consent to the processing of my personal data needed for:

#	Consent Subject	Tick box
1	My participation in a survey that will be carried out by INCENTIVE to evaluate the performance and impact of key project activities, such as outreach events and educational trainings.	

QUESTIONNAIRE

Please provide the following data.

#	Identifier	Question	Data
1	01A1.1	Number of citizens (i.e., non-professional researchers) that participated in Citizen Science (CS) projects	
2	01A1.2	Number of citizens who dropped out of the research before the CS project completes	
3	01A3.1	Number professional researchers in the CS projects	

Please reply to the following questions.

#	Identifier	Question	Very much	Somewhat	Undecided	Not really	Not at all	Don't know
1	01A6.1	Did the group of people who participated in the CS project was sufficiently large to allow a robust research?						
2	01A6.2	Were you provided with sufficient resources (e.g., infrastructure, equipment, funding, personel) to implement your research?						
3	01B4.1	Did scientists from many different disciplines (i.e., university departments) worked together on your CS project?						
4	01B4.2	Do you believe that your CS project aimed for inclusive research, implementing methods to consider the full range of human diversity with respect to ability, language, culture, gender, age and other forms of human difference?						
5	022.4	Did the CS Hub support you sufficiently with technical expertise and know-how to comply with RRI principles?						
6	01A10.4	Did you adopted any methodology for assessing the potential legal and ethical concerns related to your research and for identifying how to avoid or minimise them?						
7	025.1	Did you employ a methodology or process to anticipate and assess the impact of your research design and potential research outcomes on society, environment and economy?						

Did you receive any grants for this particular CS project? If yes, then please tell us a few words about it. (O21.4)

Was your CS project conducted in partnership or funded by a private sector actor? If yes, then please tell us a few words about it. (O3B3.2)

Which of the following constituted a key motivation for you to initiate this particular CS project? *Please select a maximum of 3 answers.*

- aligning the research question to the priorities of local society (e.g., because input from non-experts can provide you with unexpected insights) (O1A2.1)
- making a clear statement that you care about the societal impact of your research and how it works for the public (O1A9.2)
- generating impact for the citizens participating in the CS project (e.g., higher science literacy) (O1B1.3)
- building pathways by which the utility and impact of Social Sciences and Humanities research can be recognised (O1B1.2)
- making your research more accessible to a wider audience and increasing its reach (O1B2.2)
- harnessing the enthusiasm of unpaid experts for science (O1A3.3)
- resources constraints and/or funding opportunities (O1B5.1)
- time and geographic constraints and/or opportunities (e.g., they can create large data sets and complete labour-intensive tasks much faster and more efficiently) (O1B5.2)
- fulfilling career objectives and ambitions and/or gaining recognition (O1A3.4)

How many citizens were involved in the following CS project activities? *Please provide the data below.*

1	O1A4.1	data collection	
2	O1A4.2	co-definition of research questions/theme of study	
3	O1A4.3	data analysis or cleaning	
4	O1A4.4	validation of the output	
5	O1A4.5	extraction of conclusions	

Please provide the following data.

#	Identifier	Question	Data
1	O1A2.3	Number research papers that were (or expected to be) written within or after the CS project	
2	O1A7.2	Number research papers (expected to be) published in openly accessible repositories	

3	01A7.5	Number of research papers that have (or will) undergo an open peer review process (i.e., any scholarly review mechanism providing disclosure of author and referee identities to one another at any point during the peer review or publication process)	
4	01A7.1	Number of datasets that were (or expected to be) made openly available to the public within or after the CS project	
5	01A8.3	Number of publications or datasets produced by the CS project citing the names of all involved citizens	

Please reply to the following questions.

#	Identifier	Question	Yes	No
1	028.4	Did you conduct your CS project using any open-source software or open data repositories?		
2	028.5	Has your CS project developed and distributed any open-source software (or at least planning to do so)?		
3	SDG4.3	Did (or Will) your CS project produce at least one educational resource output?		
4	03B3.1	Does your CS project hold the potential to produce a marketable product or service?		
5	01A7.3	Is your CS project doing any of the following: (i) has its own website; (ii) blogs and respond to comments or feedback; (iii) has a YouTube or other video channel		
6	01A7.4	Is your CS project doing any of the following: (i) routinely upload experimental datasets to project websites, with explanatory notes and commentary; (ii) daily laboratory notebooks are written online and publicly accessible in real time; (iii) regular project dialogue, i.e., discussion between researchers, partners, and collaborators through a project wiki, is publicly accessible; (iv) employ rich virtual environments for processes of social learning and innovation		

Does your CS project research-investigate any of the following topics?

- legal and ethical matters (01A10.5)
- gender issues (SDG5.1)
- inequality problems or disadvantaged social groups projects (SDG10.2)
- urban social sustainability issues (SDG11.2)
- urban economic sustainability issues (SDG11.2)
- urban environmental sustainability issues (SDG11.2)
- circular economy or renewable energy issues (SDG12.2)

Do your CS project outputs contribute to any of the following? *Please select any that apply.*

- building resilient infrastructure, promoting sustainable industrialisation and fostering innovation (SDG9.1)
- reducing income inequalities, promoting universal social, economic and political inclusion, ensuring equal opportunities and ending discrimination (SDG10.1)
- safer and affordable housing (SDG11.1)
- affordable and sustainable transport systems (SDG11.1)
- inclusive and sustainable urbanisation (SDG11.1)
- protecting the world's cultural and natural heritage (SDG11.1)
- reducing the adverse effects of natural disasters (SDG11.1)
- reducing the environmental impact of cities (SDG11.1)
- providing access to safe and inclusive green and public spaces (SDG11.1)
- strong national and regional development planning (SDG11.1)
- policies for inclusion, resource efficiency and disaster risk reduction (SDG11.1)
- supporting least developed countries in sustainable and resilient building (SDG11.1)
- better use of resources, improving energy efficiency, green and decent jobs and ensuring a better quality of life for all (SDG12.1)
- promoting the rule of law, transparency, accountability, good governance, and non-discrimination at all levels of government (SDG16.1)
- promoting improved and more equitable trade among countries, and coordinated investment initiatives (SDG17.1)
- any of the societal challenges that the EU has identified as a priority: (i) Health, demographic change and wellbeing; (ii) Food security, sustainable agriculture and forestry, water research, and bioeconomy; (iii) Secure clean and efficient energy; (iv) Smart, green and integrated transport; (v) Climate action, environment, resource efficiency and raw material; (vi) Europe in a changing world - inclusive, innovative and reflective societies; and (vii) Secure societies - protecting freedom and security of Europe and its citizens) (O1A9.3)

You participated in this survey as a member of:

- academia or research/ education
- governmental body / regional authority
- business
- civil society organisation (such as NGO representative)
- local community
- other (please specify)

Gender: How do you identify? (SDG5.2)

- Man
- Non-binary
- Woman
- I prefer to self describe, below:

What did you like the most about running this CS project, or which were the main barriers and challenges that you faced?

Annexe 5 - CS Hub Report

Data directly captured by the CS Hub Secretary

#	Identifier	Question	Data
1	O1A1.3	Number of citizens in CS projects / Number of CS projects implemented	
2	O1B2.4	Number of (awareness-raising) events organised by the CS Hub to inform and mobilise stakeholders towards participating in CS (e.g., info days) / Total number of CS Hubs	
3	O1B2.5	Number of people that participated in the above (awareness-raising) events	
4	O21.1	Number of CS projects conducted in the RPF0 / Total number of CS Hubs	
5	O23.1	Number of other R&I activities conducted in the CS Hub with the involvement of citizens (e.g., designing, setting the agenda and/ or managing the RPF0's R&I programmes, co-creation of public policies, evaluation of research proposals applying for funding or other R&I funding decisions) / Total number of CS Hubs	
6	O23.2	Number of citizens that participated in the above R&I activities conducted in the CS Hub / Total number of RPF0s	
7	O23.5	Number of CS Hub Stakeholder Boards that include representatives of all quadrable helix stakeholder groups / Total number of CS Hubs	
8	O23.6	Number of CS Hub Stakeholder Board meetings / Total number of CS Hubs	
9	O23.7	Number of citizens that undrtook any of the following roles within the CS Hub: Secretariat; Facilitator; Community Manager; Trainer / Total number of CS Hubs	
10	O26.1	Number of capacity building activities or events (e.g., science cafés, sprints, seminars, webinars and lectures) organised to improve the capacity of citizens to creatively contribute to R&I / Total number of RPF0s	
11	O26.2	Number of citizens participated in the above capacity building activities / Total number of RPF0s	
12	O26.4	Number of activities or events organised to familiarise researchers on implementing CS projects (e.g., how to engage citizens, how to interact with them, how to utilise their contribution and the principles of CS) / Number of RPF0s	

13	026.5	Number of researchers who participated in the above activities or events / Total number of RPFOS	
14	027.2	Number of female members in the CS Hub Stakeholder Board / Total number of CS Hub Stakeholder members	
15	029.1	Number of mutual learning and networking activities (webinars, digital meetings, etc.) organised by the CS Hub ing activities to enable stakeholders connect and exchange knowledge with stakeholders from other similar initiatives / Total number of RPFOS	
16	029.2	Number of participants in the above mutual learning and networking activities / Total number of RPFOS	

Data captured through the event questionnaire

#	Identifier	Question	Data
1	01B1.4	Number of stakeholders who reported that in the future they would more actively search information about controversial technologies or read related articles and news / Total number of stakeholders surveyed	
2	01B2.6	Number of participants who reported being satisfied by the experience of participating in the awareness-raising event / Total number of participants in the above awareness-raising event	
3	01B2.7	Number of stakeholders who reported that they got involved in the CS Hub activities through a social media post / Total stakeholders surveyed	
4	01C2.3	Number of stakeholders who reported that they got involved in the CS Hub activities through a friend or contact that is already partaking in the CS Hub activities / Total number of stakeholders surveyed	
5	023.3	Number of participants who reported being satisfied by the experience of participating in the above R&I activities / Total number of participants in the above R&I activities	
6	023.8	Number of stakeholders who reported that in the future they would more actively take part in participatory processes for R&I decision-making / Total number of stakeholders surveyed	
7	026.3	Number of citizens who reported gaining sufficient knowledge from the above capacity building activities to be able participate in CS projects / Total number of citizens surveyed	
8	029.3	Number of participants who reported being satisfied by the experience of participating in the mutual learning and networking activities / Total number of participants in the above mutual learning and networking activities	
9	0210.3	Number of stakeholders who reported that participating in the CS Hub activities led or may lead to new partnerships or new networks that promote RRI / Total number of stakeholders surveyed	

10	SDG4.1	Number of citizens above 65 years old that participated in the CS projects and the capacity building activities / Total number of participants in the CS projects and the capacity building activities	
11	SDG4.2	Number of citizens below 26 years old that participated in the CS projects and the capacity building activities / Total number of participants in the CS projects and the capacity building activities	
12	O3B2.1	Number of stakeholders who reported that their participation triggered their interest in collaborating with others to solve local or global problems or to participate in relevant discussions-debates / Total number of stakeholders surveyed	
13	O3B2.2	Number of stakeholders who reported that their participation helped them to increase their interest in R&I decision-making / Total number of stakeholders surveyed	
14	O3B2.3	Number of stakeholders who reported that their participation helped them to increase their trust in science and research / Total number of stakeholders surveyed	
15	O3B4.1	Number of stakeholders perceiving CS as a legitimate way of doing research / Total number of stakeholders surveyed (KPI 9)	
16	O3B4.2	Number of stakeholders who perceive CS as a way to achieve better research results that can address social demands / Total number of stakeholders surveyed (KPI 8)	
17	O3B4.3	Number of stakeholders who perceive CS as a way to produce scientific outputs that are highly relevant to local societies needs / Total number of stakeholders surveyed (KPI 7)	
18	O3B4.4	Perceived percentage increase in stakeholders' interest in engaging in science as a result of participating in CS Hub activities (on average) (KPI 4)	

Annexe 6 - Event Questionnaire

INFORMED CONSENT FORM

Thank you for attending the recent event at our CS Hub! We are sharing with you the following questionnaire in the context of INCENTIVE, a project funded by the European Union under the Horizon 2020 Framework Programme for Research and Innovation. A detailed description of how we handle personal data is presented in the Privacy Policy that can be accessed [here](#).

CS Hub:

CS Hub name:

Address:

Phone: Email:

Responsible persons:

#	Role	Name	E-mail
1			
2			

What do we need from you?

We need you to participate in a short survey. It won't take you more than 5 minutes. Your replies will help us to evaluate the performance and impact of the key project activities. In this context, we need to process some of your personal data:

- Some basic demographics (gender, stakeholder group);

What will we do with your data?

The project's deliverables that the survey will derive will not include your personal data or any other information that could identify you. However, we are obliged to grant access to your data to:

- EU officials such as our Project Officer for purposes related to project's evaluation;
- EU agencies and other authorities for project's auditing purposes.

How can you withdraw your consent?

You can withdraw your consent at any time by communicating by email with the responsible persons listed above.

I hereby give my consent to the processing of my personal data needed for:

#	Consent Subject	Tick box
1	My participation in a survey that will be carried out by INCENTIVE to evaluate the performance and impact of key project activities, such as outreach events and educational trainings.	

QUESTIONNAIRE

#The following questions must be answered by the participants of all events-activities.

Please reply to the following questions.

#	Identifier	Question	Very much	Somewhat	Undecided	Not really	Not at all	Don't know
1	O210.3	Did meeting new people in the event led or may lead to new partnerships or new networks that promote responsible research and innovation?						
2	O3B2.1	After participating in the event, are you more interested in collaborating with others to solve local or global problems or participating in relevant discussions-debates?						
3	O3B2.3	Did the event contribute to increasing your trust in science and research?						
4	O3B4.1	Do you perceive Citizen Science (CS) as a legitimate (i.e., reasonable and ethical) way of doing research?						
5	O3B4.2	Do you perceive CS as a way to achieve better research results that can address social challenges?						
6	O3B4.3	Do you perceive CS as a way to produce scientific outputs that are highly relevant to local society's needs?						

On a scale of 1-10, how much did your interest in engaging with science increased because of participating in this event and other previous CS Hub activities? (O3B4.4)

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10

How did you get aware of this particular event?

- through a social media post (O1B2.7)
- through a friend or contact that is already partaking in the CS Hub activities (O1C2.3)
- other (please specify)

You participated in this event as a member of:

- academia or research/ education

- governmental body / regional authority
- business
- civil society organisation (such as an NGO representative)
- local community
- other (please specify)

#The following questions must be answered only by the participants of awareness-raising events or mutual learning and networking activities.

Please reply to the following question.

#	Identifier	Question	Very much	Somewhat	Undecided	Not really	Not at all	Don't know
1	01B2.6, 029.3	Are you satisfied with the experience of participating in this particular event?						

#The following questions must be answered only by the participants of capacity building events.

Please reply to the following questions.

#	Identifier	Question	Very much	Somewhat	Undecided	Not really	Not at all	Don't know
1	026.3	Did you gain sufficient knowledge from the above capacity-building event to be able to participate in a CS project?						
2	01B1.4	In the future, would you more actively search for information about controversial technologies or read related articles and news?						

What is your age range?

- <26 (SDG4.2)
- 26-45
- 46-65
- >65 (SDG4.1)

#The following questions must be answered only by the participants of R&I co-creation events.

Please reply to the following questions.

#	Identifier	Question	Very much	Somewhat	Undecided	Not really	Not at all	Don't know
1	O23.3	Are you satisfied with the experience of participating in this particular event?						
2	O3B2.2	After participating in the event, are you more interested in R&I decision-making?						
3	O23.8	In the future, would you more often take part in participatory processes for R&I decision-making?						

#The following questions must be answered by the participants of all events-activities.

What did you like the most about this event, or which aspect did you consider a weak part?

Annexe 7 - MSC Interview Template

Most Significant Change Approach Summary Report

You participated in this survey as a member of:

- academia or research/ education
- governmental body / regional authority (O1C1.4)
- business (O1C1.2)
- civil society organisation (such as NGO representative) (O1C1.3)
- local community
- other (please specify)

How have you been involved in the INCENTIVE activities? *Please select any that apply.*

- I participated in a CS project.
- I participated in the decision-making and administration of the Citizen Science (CS) Hub (e.g., as a member of the Stakeholder Board, Secretariat, or trainer).
- I participated in one or more of the events organised by the CS Hub (e.g., capacity building events, awareness-raising events, or mutual-learning events).
- I am employed, or I am studying at the university.
- None of the above applies. But, as a stakeholder, I have been in close collaboration or contact with the researchers and the personell of the CS Hub.
- other (please specify)

From your point of view, which have been the most significant changes that took place last year within the University or CS Hub in the context of the INCENTIVE project?

The INCENTIVE project, in collaboration with your university, implemented several activities to (i) facilitate the implementation of CS projects, (ii) cultivate a more scientifically interested society and (iii) promote institutional changes within the university to turn research more responsible and inclusive (by considering ethical dimensions, ensuring gender equality, engaging the public, etc.). Did you experience or observe any of these activities and changes? If yes, which one do you consider the most significant and influential for you? Please share your personal story with us in a maximum of 600 words.

What did you like the most about the INCENTIVE project and your university's work to promote CS, or which aspect did you consider a weak part?

¹ Wehn, U., Gharesifard, M. and Ceccaroni, L. (2020). D2.3: Impact-assessment methods adapted to CS. Deliverable report of project H2020 MICS

² DG for Regional Policy. (2013) EVALSED: The resource for the evaluation of Socio-Economic Development. Retrieved From: [EVALSED :The resource for the evaluation of Socio-Economic Development - Evaluation guide - Regional Policy - European Commission \(europa.eu\)](#)

³ ibid

⁴ ibid

⁵ Bloch et al. (2018) Monitoring the evolution and benefits of responsible research and innovation in Europe- Final Report, European Commission, Retrieved from: [Final report clean \(ihs.ac.at\)](#)

⁶ ibid

⁷ Van De Klippe. (2019) From MoRRI to SUPER_MoRRI: Monitoring as reflection and learning, not representation and control, CWTS, Retrieved From: [From MoRRI to SUPER MoRRI: Monitoring as reflection and learning, not representation and control \(cwts.nl\)](#)

⁸ Delaney & Iagher. (2020) Institutional changes towards responsible research and innovation, European Commission

⁹ UIA. (2020), Evaluation Approaches. Retrieved From: [Evaluation approaches | UIA - Urban Innovative Actions \(uia-initiative.eu\)](#)

¹⁰ ibid

¹¹ Wehn, U., Gharesifard, M. and Ceccaroni, L. (2020). D2.3: Impact-assessment methods adapted to CS. Deliverable report of project H2020 MICS

¹² Bloch et al. (2018) Monitoring the evolution and benefits of responsible research and innovation in Europe- Final Report, European Commission, Retrieved from: [Final report clean \(ihs.ac.at\)](#)

¹³ Strand et al. (2015) Indicators for Promoting and Monitoring Responsible Research and Innovation, European Commission. Retrieved From: [Indicators for promoting and monitoring responsible research and innovation - Publications Office of the EU \(europa.eu\)](#)

¹⁴ Wehn, U., Gharesifard, M. and Ceccaroni, L. (2020). D2.3: Impact-assessment methods adapted to CS. Deliverable report of project H2020 MICS

¹⁵ DITOs Consortium, 2016. Doing It Together science: Terms of reference and evaluation templates. UCL, London

¹⁶ Kieslinger et al. (2018) Evaluating CS: Towards an open framework. In Hecker, S., Haklay, M., Bowser, A., Makuch, Z., Vogel, J. & Bonn, A. 2018. CS: Innovation in Open Science, Society and Policy. UCL Press, London. <https://doi.org/10.14324/111.9781787352339>

¹⁷ Schaefer et al. (2021) Evaluation in CS: The Art of Tracing a Moving Target. In K. Vohland et al. (eds.), The Science of CS, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-58278-4_25

¹⁸ Coccia. (2018) An Introduction to the Theories of Institutional Change, *Journal of Economics Library* vol.5, n.4: pp 337-344

¹⁹ Delaney & Iagher. (2020) Institutional changes towards responsible research and innovation, European Commission

²⁰ DG for Regional Policy (2018) Guidance Document on Monitoring and Evaluation. Retrieved From: [guidance monitoring evaluation en.pdf \(europa.eu\)](#)

²¹ Strand et al. (2015) Indicators for Promoting and Monitoring Responsible Research and Innovation, European Commission. Retrieved From: [Indicators for promoting and monitoring responsible research and innovation - Publications Office of the EU \(europa.eu\)](#)

²² ibid

²³ ibid

²⁴ DG for Regional Policy (2018) Guidance Document on Monitoring and Evaluation. Retrieved From: [guidance_monitoring_evaluation_en.pdf \(europa.eu\)](#)

²⁵ ibid

²⁶ ibid

²⁷ Dart & Davies. (2003) A Dialogical, Story-Based Evaluation Tool: The Most Significant Change Technique, [American Journal of Evaluation](#) vol. 24, no.2, pp 137-155

²⁸ INTRAC. Most Significant Change. <https://www.intrac.org/wpcms/wp-content/uploads/2017/01/Most-significant-change.pdf>

²⁹ Voorberg, W. H., Bekkers, V. J., and Tummers, L. G. (2015). A systematic review of co-creation and co-production: Embarking on the social innovation journey. *Public Management Review*, 17(9), 1333-1357.

³⁰ Lusch, R.F., Vargo, S.L. and O'Brien, M. (2007). Competing through service: insights from service-dominant logic, *Journal of Retailing*, 83(1), 5-18.

³¹ Intersoft consulting. Principles relating to processing of personal data. Available at <https://gdpr-info.eu/art-5-gdpr/>

³² Australian Government. (2021). Set goals for your business. <https://business.gov.au/planning/business-plans/set-goals-for-your-business#:~:text=Why%20goal%20setting%20is%20important,-Goals%20are%20an&text=They%20can%20give%20you%20a,if%20your%20business%20is%20succeeding.>

ABOUT THE PROJECT

INCENTIVE aims to demonstrate the potential of citizen science through the co-creation, establishment and assessment of Citizen Science Hubs in four EU Universities: University of Twente (NL), Autonomous University of Barcelona (ES), Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (EL) and Vilnius Gediminas Technical University (LT).

By doing so, the project accelerates the transition of these institutions to more inclusive, open and democratic innovation and scientific governance, under the principles of Responsible Research and Innovation. The project seeks to deliver a legacy to European and international research institutes on how to create and operate their own Hub with the aim to secure a sustainable future.

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